

BioCompWaterClean Workshop

New applications in wastewater treatment
on the way to zero-waste technology

20-21 October, 2025, Novi Sad, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Title: Book of Abstracts of BioCompWaterClean Project Workshop
“New Applications in Wastewater Treatment on the Way to
Zero-Waste Technology”

Published by: University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Bulevar cara Lazara 1, Novi Sad, Serbia

For publisher: Prof. Dr. Zita Šereš, Dean,
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia

Editors: Dr. Mirjana Petronijević, Prof. Dr. Slavica Ražić

**This publication is
financially supported by:** Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia

CIP - Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Matice srpske, Novi Sad

628.3/4(048.3)

628.16(048.3)

BIO Comp Water Clean Workshop "New applications in wastewater treatment on the way to zero-waste technology" (1 ; 2025 ; Novi Sad)

Book of abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / Bio Comp Water Clean Workshop "New applications in wastewater treatment on the way to zero-waste technology", 20-21st 2025, Novi Sad ; [editors Mirjana Petronijević, Slavica Ražić]. - Novi Sad : Tehnološki fakultet, 2025

Način pristupa (URL): <https://biocompwaterclean.org/>. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan 3.11.2025. - Nasl. sa naslovnog ekrana.

ISBN 978-86-6253-197-1

COBISS.SR-ID 179243529

BIOCOMPWATERCLEAN WORKSHOP

NEW APPLICATIONS IN WASTEWATER
TREATMENT ON THE WAY TO ZERO-
WASTE TECHNOLOGY

Science and Technology Park Novi Sad
20-21 October, 2025, Novi Sad,
Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

ORGANISATION

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Slavica Ražić – Chair, Full Professor, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Serbia

Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić,
Principal Research Fellow, University of
Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia

Sanja Panić, Senior Research Associate,
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of
Technology, Serbia

Ioannis Katsoyiannis, Full Professor,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki,
Department of Chemistry, Greece

Vanessa Pereira, Assistant Researcher,
iBET - Instituto de Biologia Experimental
e Tecnológica, Lisboa, Portugal

Martin Vyšvařil, Assistant Professor,
Brno University of Technology, Institute
of Chemistry, Faculty of Civil
Engineering, Czech Republic

Biljana Lončar, Principal Research
Fellow, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of
Technology, Serbia

Mirjana Petronijević, Senior Research
Associate, University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Technology, Serbia

Nenad Grba, Senior Research Associate,
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of
Sciences, Serbia

Olívia Soares, Assistant Researcher,
University of Porto, Faculty of
Engineering, Portugal

Zoran Petrović, Full Professor,
University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of
Technology, Zvornik, Republic of Srpska

Sabina Begić, Full Professor, University
of Tuzla, Faculty of Technology, Bosnia
and Hercegovina

Gokhan Zengin, Associate Professor,
Selcuk University, Science Faculty,
Department of Biology Campus/Konya,
Turkey

Ashok Kumar Nadda, Assistant
Professor, Jaypee University of
Information Technology, Department of
Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, India

Laura Ricciotti, Assistant Professor,
University of Campania, Department of
Architecture and Industrial Design, Italy

Dragana Mutavdžić Pavlović, Full
Professor, University of Zagreb, Faculty
of Chemical Engineering and Technology,
Croatia

ORGANISING COMMITTEE

Mirjana Petronjević - Chair, Senior Research Associate, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia

Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić,
Principal Research Fellow, University of
Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Serbia

Jelena Tanasić, Research Associate,
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of
Technology, Serbia

Sanja Panić, Senior Research Associate,
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of
Technology, Serbia

Milena Terzić, Senior Research
Associate, University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Technology, Serbia

Jovana Topalić, Research Associate,
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of
Technical Sciences, Serbia

Jelena Arsenijević, Senior Research
Associate, University of Belgrade, Faculty
of Pharmacy, Serbia

Svetlana Đogo Mračević, Associate
Professor, University of Belgrade, Faculty
of Pharmacy, Serbia

Marina Škondrić, Assistant Professor,
University of Belgrade, Faculty of Civil
Engineering, Serbia

WORKSHOP VENUE

Science and Technology Park Novi Sad,
Fruškogorska 1, 21102 Novi Sad

CONTACT

office@biocompwaterclean.org

WELCOME

On behalf of the Scientific and Organizing Committee, it is our great pleasure to warmly welcome you to the BioCompWaterClean Workshop, “New applications in wastewater treatment on the way to zero-waste technology”.

In a world facing the greatest challenges of current and future generations, innovation in water treatment and clean water is not just a scientific and professional task—it is also a social responsibility. In this context, and in line with current global demands and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the BioCompWaterClean Workshop aims to add value by providing high-quality knowledge exchange that contributes particularly to SDG 4 (quality education) and SDG 6 (clean water and sanitation).

Multidisciplinary teams of researchers and experts in various fields of chemistry and technology will present at this two-day international workshop, sharing innovative methodologies and advances in processes for wastewater treatment, pollutant removal, new materials, and potential solutions for zero-waste technologies or waste material utilization and valorization. These efforts generate new resources to ensure the sustainable management of water and improve water quality.

Furthermore, the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and problem-solving ideas may drive new initiatives for further cooperation and joint projects.

Enjoy sharing your valuable time with us!

Prof. Dr. Slavica Ražić
BioCompWaterClean Project Leader

INDEX

PLENARY LECTURES

Ioannis Katsoyiannis

NOVEL APPROACHES FOR CHROMIUM (VI) AND ARSENIC
REMOVAL FROM GROUNDWATERS2

Đurđa Kerkez

A DECISION-MAKING FRAMEWORK FOR SUSTAINABLE SEWAGE
SLUDGE MANAGEMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA:
CIRCULAR ECONOMY PERSPECTIVES4

Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares

DESIGN OF CARBON-BASED CATALYSTS FOR ADVANCED WATER
TREATMENT PROCESSES.....6

INVITED LECTURES

Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević, Slavica Ražić

SUSTAINABLE CATALYTIC STRATEGIES FOR PERSULFATE-BASED
OXIDATION OF PHENOLIC POLLUTANTS IN WASTEWATER9

**Jovana Pešić Bajić, Jasmina Nikić, Jasmina Agbaba, Marko Solić,
Malcolm Watson**

EXPLORING GRAPHENE OXIDE ADSORPTION FOR EFFECTIVE
HEAVY METAL REMOVAL FROM WATER10

**Dragana Lukić, Vesna Vasić, Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Sanja Panić,
Mirjana Petronijević, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović**

TURNING WASTE INTO VALUE: SUSTAINABLE BIOSORBENTS
FOR MODERN WASTEWATER CHALLENGES11

**Nikola Maravić, Jelena Šurlan, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Nataša
Đurišić-Mladenović, Zita Šereš**

REMOVAL OF ANTIBIOTICS FROM MUNICIPAL WASTEWATER BY
USING COUPLED MEMBRANE PROCESSES12

Petar Pižurica

WWTP SUBOTICA MUNICIPAL WASTEWATER - ON THE WAY FROM
WASTE TO RESOURCE13

**Nadiia Khakimova, Nikola Maravić, Petar Davidović, Dajana
Blagojević, Milena Bečelić-Tomin, Jelica Simeunović, Vesna Pešić, Zita
Šereš, Anamarija Mandić, Milica Pojić, Aleksandra Mišan**

FROM WASTEWATER TO RESOURCE: THE POTENTIAL OF
MICROALGAE FOR TREATING SUGAR INDUSTRY WASTEWATER14

Nenad Grba, Vesna Vasić, Miloš Dubovina COST-BENEFIT EVALUATION OF THE ADSORPTION MEDIA EFFICIENCY AT A PILOT PLANT FOR GROUNDWATER TREATMENT	15
Vesna Vasić, Dragana Lukić, Ivana Čabarkapa, Slađana Rakita, Jasmina Lazarević "FROM WASTE TO RESOURCE" – DANUBEcare	16
Tijana Marjanović Srebro, Jasmina Anojčić, Sanja Mutić, Nina Đukanović, Tamara Apostolović, Sabolč Bognar, Jelena Beljin REUSABILITY OF BIOCHAR AS A CATALYST IN PERSULFATE SYSTEMS FOR ATRAZINE AND SIMAZINE DEGRADATION	17
Nataša Slijepčević, Dragana Tomašević Pilipović, Boris Agarski, Miloš Šešlija, Milana Ilić Mićunović EVALUATION OF STABILIZED DREDGED SEDIMENT'S POTENTIAL FOR USE IN SUBGRADE MATERIAL WITH LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT	18
Dunja Rađenović Veselić, Dragana Tomašević Pilipović, Đurđa Kerkez FROM CONTAMINATED SEDIMENTS TO SAFE REUSE: LONG- TERM STABILIZATION AND SOLIDIFICATION	19
Aleksandra Tubić, Maja Vujić, Sanja Vasiljević UNDERSTANDING MICROPLASTIC POLLUTION IN AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS AND STRATEGIES FOR REMOVAL THROUGH WATER TREATMENT	20
Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović TwiNSol-CECs: ENHANCING WESTERN BALKAN CAPACITIES FOR EMERGING CONTAMINANTS MONITORING AND REMOVAL FROM WATER SYSTEMS TOWARD ZERO POLLUTION	21
Ivana Danilov, Jovana Grahovac, Vanja Vlajkov, Snežana Vučetić, Bojan Miljević, Vesna Miljić VALORIZATION OF EFFLUENTS FROM URBAN WASTEWATER TREATMENT BY DEVELOPING BIOPROCESS SOLUTIONS FOR BIOFERTILIZERS AND BIOMATERIALS PRODUCTION	22
Tamara Erceg, Vanja Travčić, Vesna Teofilović, Milica Aćimović, Gordana Četković ECO-FRIENDLY CONCEPT FOR THE CONTROL OF INVASIVE STINK BUGS	23
Ivan Stijepović, Marija Milanović, Vesna Vasić, Dragana Lukić NEW ZEOLITE FILTER FOR REMOVAL OF ARSENIC FROM WATER	24

SESSION I - INNOVATIONS IN WATER AND WASTEWATER TREATMENT

Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Nenad Grba, Jelena Tanasić, Laura Ricciotti, Svetlana Đogo Mračević, Slavića Ražić ^[PP]

ALLOPHANE-BENTONITE BASED GEOPOLYMER AS FAST-ACTING ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF MANGANESE IONS FROM WATER.....26

Halid Junuzović, Sabina Begić, Amra Selimović, Indira Šestan, Melisa Ahmetović, Ervin Karić ^[PP]

INFLUENCE OF MIXING SPEED AND CONTACT TIME ON HYDROXIDE PRECIPITATION OF SELECTED METALS27

Stella Chatzimichailidou, Maria Xanthopoulou, and Ioannis Katsoyiannis ^[OP]

SUSTAINABLE GROUNDWATER DECONTAMINATION OF ARSENIC USING A RICE HUSK-IRON OXIDE COMPOSITE AND ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESS28

Andromachi Charizani, Natalia Malouchi, Konstantinos Plakas, Ioannis Katsoyiannis ^[OP]

ADSORPTION OF CAFFEINE ON GRANULAR ACTIVATED CARBON AND IN SITU REGENERATION OF THE ADSORBENT BY FENTON-TYPE ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESSES29

Natalia Malouchi, Stella Chatzimichailidou, Veroniki Bakola, Olympia Kotrotsiou, Konstantinos V. Plakas, Ioannis A. Katsoyiannis ^[OP]

ADVANCED LAYER-BY-LAYER MODIFIED ULTRAFILTRATION MEMBRANES FOR EFFICIENT CR(VI) REMOVAL FROM WATER31

Maria Xanthopoulou, Andromachi Charizani, Dimitrios Gkiliopoulos, Konstantinos S. Triantafyllidis, Margaritis Kostoglou, and Ioannis A. Katsoyiannis ^[OP]

IMPACT OF NATURAL WATER CONSTITUENTS ON THE ADSORPTION OF Cr(VI) BY POLYETHYLENIMINE-MODIFIED SILICA33

Marija Šobić, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Igor Antić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović ^[PP]

APPLICATION OF HYDROCHAR AS ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF FAMOTIDINE FROM WATER34

Dimitra Karagiannidi, Ourania Epoglou ^[PP]

DEVELOPMENT OF A PILOT UNIT WITH SMART MEMBRANES AND INNOVATIVE ADSORBENT MATERIALS FOR THE REMOVAL OF HEXAVALENT CHROMIUM FROM WATER35

Teodora Subić, Dragana Lukić, Vesna Vasić, Marko Ilić, Srdjan Stojnić, Saša Orlović ^[PP]

INTEGRATING FORESTRY RESOURCES INTO WASTEWATER TREATMENT: ADSORPTIVE POTENTIAL OF VARIOUS TREE SPECIES FOR CHROMIUM(VI) REMOVAL37

Klára Novotná, Karel Hrich, Jitka Malá ^[PP]	
ADSORPTION OF METOLACHLOR ON WOODCHIPS	38
Đurđica Karanović, Milica Hadnađev-Kostić, Tatjana Vulić ^[OP]	
MIXED OXIDES AS PHOTOCATALYSTS FOR DEGRADATION OF BINARY DYE SYSTEMS IN WATER SOLUTIONS	39
Jasmina Nikić, Marko Šolić, Jovana Pešić Bajić, Jovana Jokić Govedarica, Malcolm Watson, Jasmina Agbaba ^[PP]	
MAGNETIC BIOCHAR FOR WATER TREATMENT: A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO Cr(VI) REMOVAL	40
Nebojša Vasiljević, Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević, Nataša Đurišić Mladenović ^[OP]	
VALORIZATION OF RED MUD AS CATALYST IN FENTON SYSTEMS	41
Vladimir Šaraba, Dajana Lazarević, Jelena Jovanović, Ivana Jovanić, Tatjana Trtić-Petrović ^[PP]	
PYROPHYLLITE SCHIST – A NATURAL PURIFIER FOR ZINC REMOVAL FROM WATER	42
Kriti Sharma, Ashok Kumar Nadda ^[OP]	
SUSTAINABLE POLLUTANT REMOVAL AND RESOURCE RECOVERY USING MICROALGAE TETRADESMUS OBLIQUUS FROM THE TRANS- HIMALAYAN REGION: A CIRCULAR ECONOMY APPROACH	43
Nataša Gajić, Dragana Radovanović, Marija Štulović ^[PP]	
SUSTAINABLE WASTEWATER TREATMENT: UTILIZATION OF BIO-WASTE IN LEAD AND COPPER REMOVAL	44
Milan Glišić, Ljiljana Tanasić ^[PP]	
METAGENOMIC INSIGHTS INTO MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES DRIVING NITROGEN AND PHOSPHORUS REMOVAL IN CONSTRUCTED WETLANDS.....	45
Mirhad Bošnjaković, Milan Glišić, Jelena Robinić, Ljiljana Tanasić ^[PP]	
ANALYSIS OF THE STATE AND PERSPECTIVES OF IMPROVING THE TREATMENT OF WASTEWATER FROM DAIRIES IN SERBIA	46
Radivoj Tomić, Nenad Grba, Višnja Mihajlović and Slaven Tenodi ^[PP]	
METHODOLOGY PROPOSALS FOR LONG-TERM MONITORING OF HIGHLY POLLUTED WATER BODIES	47
Dušan Rakić, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić- Mladenović ^[PP]	
TARGET ANALYSIS OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN IN SURFACE WATER OF THE GREAT BAČKA CANAL	48
Stefan Marković, Nenad Pavlović, Nemanja Stošić, Vera Rašković ^[PP]	
ORGANIC PRODUCTION IN ORDER TO CONSERVE WATER	49
Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić, Biljana Lončar, Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Dušan Rakić, Nenad Grba, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović ^[PP]	
APPLICATION OF HYDROPHOBIC NATURAL DEEP EUTECTIC SOLVENTS FOR ORGANIC MICROPOLLUTANTS REMOVAL FROM WATER –WaDES project	50

SESSION II - PROCESSES SUITABLE FOR ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

Jovana Topalić, Slavica Ražić ^[OP]

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS AS A DECISION-SUPPORT TOOL FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF INNOVATIVE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS52

Jelena Beljin, Nina Đukanović, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Dragana Tamindžija, Stanko Milić, Tijana Zeremski, Snežana Maletić ^[OP]

MICROBIAL-ASSISTED PHYTOREMEDIATION STRATEGIES FOR HEAVY METAL REMOVAL FROM POLLUTED SOILS53

Dragana Žmukić, Anita Leovac Maćerak, Đurđa Kerkez, Tamara Erceg ^[PP]

WASTEWATER AS A SOURCE OF POLYHYDROXYALKANOATES54

Vedran Stuhli, Alma Huremović, Mirnesa Čorbić, Hana Alihodžić, Maida Smajlović, Ljilja Bojanović ^[PP]

BIOREMEDIATION OF LEACHATE FROM MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE LANDFILLS55

Marina Škondrić, Aleksandar Savić, Aleksandar Radević ^[PP]

USE OF WASTEWATER SLUDGE AND OTHER WATER TREATMENT BY-PRODUCTS IN MORTAR AND CONCRETE PRODUCTION56

Sengul Uysal, Gokhan Zengin, Ugur Cakilcioglu, Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić ^[PP]

EUPHORBIA MACROCLADA BOISS: PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES57

Milena Terzić, Biljana Lončar, Aleksadra Cvetanović Kljakić, Gokhan Zengin, Jelena Arsenijević, Slavica Ražić ^[PP]

VALORIZATION OF STRAWBERRY WASTE USING ULTRASOUND ASSISTED EXTRACTION AND ANN MODELLING58

Biljana Lončar, Milena Terzić, Aleksadra Cvetanović Kljakić, Mirjana Petronijević, Gokhan Zengin, Jelena Arsenijević, Slavica Ražić ^[PP]

APPLE WASTE OPTIMIZATION USING ULTRASOUND ASSISTED EXTRACTION-MATEMATICAL MODELLING APPROACH59

Jelena Tanasić, Vladan Mičić, Ivan Ristić ^[PP]

ECO-FUNCTIONAL ACRYLAMIDE COPOLYMERS FOR SUSTAINABLE WASTEWATER TREATMENT60

Vesna Teofilović, Danka Radić, Snežana Štrbac, Sebastian Primpke, Nataša Stojić ^[PP]

IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION OF A PHASED TRAINING COURSE FOR COMPREHENSIVE MICROPLASTIC ANALYSIS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES61

ABOUT BIOCOMPWATERCLEAN PROJECT62

PLENARY LECTURES

Ioannis Katsoyiannis
Full Professor,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki,
Department of Chemistry
Greece

Ioannis Katsoyiannis is a Full Professor at the department of Chemistry of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Director of the Institute of Sustainable Water Management and Water Law of the European Public Law Organization and President of the Hellenic Industrial Property Academy. He used to be the President of the Association of Greek Chemists, Chair of the Division of Chemistry and Environment of the European Chemical Society (EuChemS) and Executive Board Member of EuChemS. Currently is representing EuChemS at the Zero Pollution Stakeholders Platform of the European Commission.

In the past, Prof. Katsoyiannis was a recipient of prestigious international fellowships, such as from Alexander von Humboldt Foundation, the IKY, the DAAD, and the Swiss National Science Foundation. He is the author of more than 100 research papers, which have received more than 8300 citations. He is scientific responsible in several research projects with an accumulative budget of more than 2.5 million euros and has been invited more than 40 times to give lectures worldwide in international conferences. In March 2023, during the UN water conference, he gave a statement about the world water situation, at the General Assembly of the United Nations in New York.

Professor Katsoyiannis, since 2022 is serving as an academic advisor for the Onassis Foundation and is associate editor for the Journal Environmental Science and Pollution Research (Springer).

NOVEL APPROACHES FOR CHROMIUM (VI) AND ARSENIC REMOVAL FROM GROUNDWATERS

Ioannis A. Katsoyiannis

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Chemistry, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece.

* katsogia@chem.auth.gr

Abstract

Chromium (VI) and arsenic contamination of groundwaters is still a matter of concern in several countries across the world, among which also Balkan countries, such as Serbia and Greece. Treatment of drinking water for chromium (Cr) and arsenic (As) removal has been implemented in centralized facilities worldwide, reflecting the increasingly stringent national and international drinking water standards for these compounds, for which a standard of 10 µg/L and 25 µg/L has been adopted by the European Union. In this presentation, the most common technologies widely applied for their removal will be presented, while novel developments of our group will be shown, such as the use of membranes for their removal or the use of novel modified materials. We will also show results for the simultaneous removal of Cr(VI) and arsenic, which have a great interest also from the point of view of aquatic chemistry.

Key words: Cr(VI), arsenic, adsorption, oxidation

Acknowledgment: We acknowledge support of this work by the project “Hybrid technologies of smart membranes and novel materials for the removal of hexavalent chromium from water” (YII3TA-0560800) which is implemented under the action “SUB1.1: Clusters of Research Excellence” of the sub-action “Strategy for Excellence in Universities & Innovation” (ID 16289), Greece 2.0 – National Recovery and Resilience Fund and funded by European Union Next Generation EU.

Đurđa Kerkez
Full Professor,
University of Novi Sad,
Faculty of Sciences
Republic of Serbia

Dr. Đurđa Kerkez is a full professor at the Faculty of Science, University of Novi Sad, at the Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection. Her scientific and research work is in the field of water quality, with a focus on improved wastewater treatment. She is the author and co-author of over 45 scientific papers in journals of international importance, as well as a large number of announcements at international and national conferences.

Scientific work is carried out through numerous international and national projects, as well as through cooperation projects with the economy. She managed the WasteWaterForce project from PROMIS, the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, as well as the CarbIrON project in cooperation with the Joint Research Center, and through them various innovative materials for wastewater treatment were developed. Currently, he manages the SmartWaterTwin project from Horizon Europe, which deals with the observation of wastewater through the framework of the circular economy, as well as Soil Sentinel, a citizen-science project exploring the potential for sewage sludge agricultural application.

She is the author and co-author of 11 textbooks, auxiliary textbooks and practicums, the most recent of which are the books Wastewater in the context of social challenges (2022) and Technological and resource aspects of the circular model of sludge management from water treatment (2024). Activities for both the scientific and wider social community are achieved through membership in the Serbian Chemical Society, the International Water Association - IWA and the Association for water technology and sanitary engineering. She is also the member of the steering committee of the Educational center for environmental protection EDEN.

A DECISION-MAKING FRAMEWORK FOR SUSTAINABLE SEWAGE SLUDGE MANAGEMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA: CIRCULAR ECONOMY PERSPECTIVES

Djordja Kerkez*, Milena Bečelić-Tomin, Vesna Pešić, Anita Leovac Maćerak, Dragana Tomašević Pilipović

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21102 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

* djurdja.kerkez@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

The sewage sludge management is a key challenge for implementing circular economy principles in the wastewater sector. In the Republic of Serbia, the Regulation on the management of sludge from municipal wastewater treatment plants (Official Gazette RS, 103/2023) introduced stricter rules for sludge use, partly harmonized with the EU Sewage Sludge Directive (86/278/EEC) and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Despite this progress, selecting suitable treatment and reuse options remains complex, requiring decisions that balance environmental, technological, socio-economic, and regulatory factors. Decision-support framework for sludge management in the Republic of Serbia must integrate criteria such as sludge quantity and composition, pollutant and pathogen levels, energy and material recovery potential, regulatory compliance, cost-effectiveness, and social acceptance. Drawing on European best practices, the framework should compare key technological options including agricultural application, composting, anaerobic digestion, incineration, and advanced thermal treatments. Life-cycle assessment indicators such as greenhouse gas emissions, ecotoxicity, and nutrient recovery efficiency are also incorporated to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of environmental performance. The proposed framework supports evidence-based decisions that can transform wastewater treatment plants into resource recovery facilities. By aligning Serbian practice with EU circular economy principles, this approach enhances water security, promotes sustainable agriculture, and contributes to climate resilience in the Western Balkans.

Key words: *sewage sludge management, circular economy, resource recovery, regulatory framework*

Acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, Horizon Europe – Work Programme 2021-2022 Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area, HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02, under grant agreement No [101060110], SmartWaterTwin.

Olívia Soares
Assistant Researcher,
University of Porto,
Faculty of Engineering
Portugal

Olívia Salomé Gonçalves Pinto Soares, Assistant Researcher at the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto, ALiCE - Associate Laboratory in Chemical Engineering and LSRE-LCM Laboratory of Separation and Reaction Engineering - Laboratory of Catalysis and Materials, Portugal.

Salomé Soares has a background in the field of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, focused on heterogeneous catalysis, having relevant experience in the design of nanostructured materials, metal-free, supported metal or metal oxide catalysts, as well as in their application in environmental technologies (water/wastewater treatments, abatement of air pollutants), CO₂ valorisation, electrochemical energy conversion, and smart textiles.

She co-authored more than 184 publications in ISI-indexed papers (H-index 41) and more than 300 communications in conference proceedings and co-inventor of 4 patent applications. She is regularly involved in supervising activities, with 30 MSc students (29 concluded) and 15 PhD students (5 concluded), 3 postdoctoral researchers, and 15 research fellows. She is the principal researcher at FEUP of 1 national project and has led 1 national and 1 international research project, both of which were led by companies. Additionally, she has participated as a team member in 31 national projects (6 of which were led by companies) and 3 international projects.

DESIGN OF CARBON-BASED CATALYSTS FOR ADVANCED WATER TREATMENT PROCESSES

Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares

LSRE-LCM, ALiCE, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto, Rua Dr. Roberto Frias, 4200-465 Porto, Portugal

* salome.soares@fe.up.pt

Abstract

Heterogeneous catalysis, applied for water treatment, has been widely studied for the removal of several organic and inorganic contaminants present in water [1]. Although different reaction conditions and catalysts are necessary to remove both types of pollutants, this methodology appears as a simpler, efficient, and more economical alternative to perform the definitive remediation of different classes of contaminants.

Carbon materials have become particularly attractive in this context, as they can serve as both catalyst supports and catalysts on their own. Their intrinsic properties — such as high resistance to acidic and basic media, tunable textural and surface characteristics, and the facile recovery of precious metals by combustion — make them excellent candidates for catalytic applications. Textural and chemical modifications through liquid- or gas-phase treatments, mechanical activation, or solid-state reactions enable the development of materials with tailored surface functionalities and enhanced catalytic performance [2].

This work explores the versatility of carbon materials in environmental catalysis, with a focus on their applications as metal supports or metal-free catalysts in ion reduction and advanced oxidation processes.

Reference

- [1] J. Restivo, O.S.G.P. Soares, M.F.R. Pereira, in *From Nano- to Macrostructured Carbon Catalysts for Water and Wastewater Treatment*, M. Piumetti and S. Bensaid, (Eds.), Switzerland, Springer, 2021, 273.
- [2] R.P. Rocha, O.S.G.P. Soares, J.L. Figueiredo, M.F.R. Pereira, “Tuning CNT Properties for Metal-Free Environmental Catalytic Applications”, *C -Journal of Carbon Research*, 2016, 2, 17.

Keywords: *heterogeneous catalysis, water treatment, carbon materials,*

Acknowledgment:

This work was financially supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P. /MCTES through national funds: LSRE-LCM, UID/50020/2025; and ALiCE, LA/P/0045/2020 (DOI: 10.54499/LA/P/0045/2020).

INVITED LECTURES

SUSTAINABLE CATALYTIC STRATEGIES FOR PERSULFATE-BASED OXIDATION OF PHENOLIC POLLUTANTS IN WASTEWATER

Sanja Panić^{1*}, Mirjana Petronijević¹, Slavica Ražić²

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Vojvode Stepe 450, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

* sanjar@tf.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Phenolic compounds are among the most hazardous classes of organic contaminants in industrial effluents due to their high toxicity, persistence, and resistance to conventional biological treatment. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) based on persulfate activation have emerged as promising technologies for their degradation, offering efficient generation of sulfate and hydroxyl radicals under mild conditions. Recent research has increasingly focused on the development of green heterogeneous catalysts that not only enhance persulfate activation but also align with the principles of sustainability, resource efficiency, and environmental safety. This review summarizes the latest advances in the rational design of heterogeneous catalysts, particularly carbon-based materials, biochar, metal oxides, and hybrid composites, with emphasis on eco-friendly synthesis routes, surface modification strategies, and structural features that govern activity, selectivity, and stability [1,2]. Special attention is given to catalysts derived from renewable biomass and waste precursors, as well as to the dual role of surface functionalities in pollutant adsorption and radical generation. Current challenges, including catalyst deactivation, metal leaching, and secondary pollution, are critically discussed alongside strategies to address them. Finally, future perspectives highlight the need for scalable synthesis, life cycle assessment, and integration of persulfate-based AOPs into hybrid treatment systems for practical wastewater remediation.

References:

[1] Wang, G., Kou, L., Li, C., Xu, B., Wu, Y. *Nanomaterials*, 15(13) (2025) 979.

[2] Huang, R., Feng, T., Wu, S., Zhang, X., Fan, Z., Yu, Q., Chen, Y., Chen, T. *Environ Res.* 234 (2023) 116604.

Keywords: *persulfate activation, green heterogeneous catalysts, phenolic compounds, wastewater treatment*

Acknowledgment: *This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No 7464, Novel Bio-linked Magnetite/geopolymer Composites in Phenol-containing Wastewater Treatment: Toward Zero-waste Technology - BioCompWaterClean.*

EXPLORING GRAPHENE OXIDE ADSORPTION FOR EFFECTIVE HEAVY METAL REMOVAL FROM WATER

Jovana Pešić Bajić¹, Jasmina Nikić¹, Jasmina Agbaba¹, Marko Šolić¹, Malcolm Watson^{1*}

¹University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

* Corresponding author: malcolm.watson@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

With climate change intensifying water scarcity and a rapidly growing global population increasing demand for clean water, protecting freshwater resources is more critical than ever. The widespread presence of heavy metals in wastewater streams is of particular concern, as their toxicity poses serious risks to human health and ecosystems. Effective removal of heavy metals supports sustainable water management by enabling reuse of reclaimed water and sludge generated by wastewater treatment plants. This work therefore details the synthesis of graphene oxide (GO), and explores its adsorption kinetics and capacity for lead removal from water. GO was synthesised using a modified version of Hummer's method, and a series of batch adsorption experiments were carried out in a synthetic water matrix. Kinetics experiments showed that the system quickly reached equilibrium after a few minutes. Fitting the isotherm data with Langmuir's model gave a maximum Pb adsorption capacity q_{max} of 96.7 mg Pb/g GO. These results demonstrate that GO is an extremely promising adsorbent for lead removal from wastewater. Future work will focus on scaling up and optimising the GO synthesis process, to prepare sufficient adsorbent to carry out continuous flow experiments on real world lead-contaminated waste streams, such as wastewaters from the metallurgy, energy storage or pigment industries.

Key words: *graphene oxide, lead, adsorption, water treatment*

Acknowledgment: *The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125)*

TURNING WASTE INTO VALUE: SUSTAINABLE BIOSORBENTS FOR MODERN WASTEWATER CHALLENGES

Dragana Lukić*, Vesna Vasić, Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević,
Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

* dkukic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Contamination of water resources with both traditional and emerging organic compounds (CEC) poses a serious threat to the environment and human health. Among the wide range of available technologies, biosorption has gained attention as a promising alternative to conventional wastewater treatment methods due to its low cost and efficiency. Moreover, converting waste biomass into functional sorbents supports sustainable wastewater treatment and aligns with the principles of resource recovery and circular economy.

This paper presents selected results from recent studies on the preparation and application of a series of biosorbents obtained from waste lignocellulosic materials. A comparative assessment was performed on biosorbents derived from raspberry canes, including native waste biomass [1], lignin [2], lignin isolation residues, and biochar. The biosorbents were evaluated for Cr(VI) removal and CEC. Experiments were conducted in both synthetic solutions and real wastewater samples. High Cr(VI) removal was observed for native and modified biomass, and lignin, while the removal of organic pollutants varied depending on compound and matrix properties. Notably, raspberry-derived biochar showed high performance in real wastewater samples for the removal of CEC.

These results demonstrate the potential of converting low-value waste into efficient biosorbents. Such approaches support the shift toward more circular and sustainable wastewater treatment strategies by coupling pollution mitigation with resource recovery.

[1] D. Kukić, A. Ivanovska, V. Vasić, J. Lađarević, M. Kostić, M. Šćiban, *Biomass Conv. Bioref.* 2024,14, 4605–4619.

[2] A. Lourenço, D. Kukić, V. Vasić, R.A. Costa, M. Antov, M. Šćiban, J. Gominho, *Molecules*, 2022, 27, 6246.

Key words: biosorbents, wastewater, organic pollutants, heavy metals, chromium

Acknowledgment: The authors acknowledge the support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia for funding this research (program No. 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200134 and 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200134) and the TwiNSol-CECs project, which has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement no.101059867.

REMOVAL OF ANTIBIOTICS FROM MUNICIPAL WASTEWATER BY USING COUPLED MEMBRANE PROCESSES

Nikola Maravić, Jelena Šurlan, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Zita Šereš

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

* maravic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

The presence of antibiotics in municipal wastewater represents a growing environmental and public health concern, as their continuous release can promote the spread of antibiotic resistance and negatively impact aquatic ecosystems. Conventional wastewater treatment plants are not specifically designed to efficiently remove micropollutants such as antibiotics, which highlights the need for advanced treatment technologies. In this study, the effectiveness of coupled membrane processes for the removal of two macrolide antibiotics, clarithromycin and erythromycin, from municipal wastewater was investigated. A two-step approach was employed, combining ultrafiltration (UF) as a pretreatment stage with nanofiltration (NF) as a final step. The results demonstrated that the integrated UF–NF system achieved high removal efficiencies for both antibiotics. Specifically, clarithromycin and erythromycin removals exceeded 85%. In addition, the coupling of UF prior to NF contributed to stable operational performance by minimizing fouling and maintaining permeate flux. The obtained results suggest that membrane-based treatment represents a promising strategy for the mitigation of antibiotic contamination in municipal wastewater and reducing the risks associated with the emission of antibiotic residues into the environment.

Key words: *antibiotics, clarithromycin, erythromycin, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration, municipal wastewater, membrane processes*

Acknowledgment: *Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EU executive agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This work is conducted under the project TwiNSol-CECs that has received funding from Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement no.101059867.*

WWTP SUBOTICA MUNICIPAL WASTEWATER - ON THE WAY FROM WASTE TO RESOURCE

Petar Pižurica

PUC “Waterworks & Sewerage” Subotica, Serbia

[*pizurica@vodovodsu.rs](mailto:pizurica@vodovodsu.rs)

Abstract

The use of wastewater as a resource is a key step towards sustainable water management and environmental protection. Instead of viewing wastewater exclusively as a burden and environmental problem, modern approaches increasingly recognize it as a valuable source of water, energy and nutrients. This concept fits into the principles of the circular economy, where resources are used efficiently and repeatedly, thus reducing the pressure on natural resources.

This paper presents those parts of the treatment of municipal wastewater at WWTP Subotica, which can generate "products" usable as a resource either raw, or through further processing. Some of these “products” are: treated waste water which can be used for irrigation, due to its nutrient content, sludge which together with green biomass can be used as a raw material for obtaining compost, and separated bio-gas from the anaerobic digestion as an energy source for combustion on CHP units for the production of heat and electricity.

The work is focused on the problems, solutions, examples of good practice established during the work of the WWTP Subotica and future moves to improve the water quality in the lakes Palić and Ludaš.

Picture 1. WWTP Subotica

Keywords: Wastewater, irrigation, compost, biogas, resource.

FROM WASTEWATER TO RESOURCE: THE POTENTIAL OF MICROALGAE FOR TREATING SUGAR INDUSTRY WASTEWATER

Nadiia Khakimova¹, Nikola Maravić², Petar Davidović¹, Dajana Blagojević¹, Milena Bečelić-Tomin³, Jelica Simeunović¹, Vesna Pešić³, Zita Šereš², Anamarija Mandić⁴, Milica Pojić⁴, Aleksandra Mišan^{4*}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Biology and Ecology, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Bul. Cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

⁴University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology, Bul. Cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

* aleksandra.misan@fins.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

One of the major environmental challenges today is the contamination of surface waters by effluents from the food industry. In many sugar-producing regions, efficient water management is crucial to minimizing both water consumption and pollutant discharge. Given the seasonal nature of sugar production, there is a need for simple and cost-effective treatment solutions. In this study, the potential integration of microalgae biomass production into sugar beet wastewater treatment was investigated. A selected microalgal strain was cultivated in wastewater collected from a sugar beet processing plant at the beginning and end of the production campaign. The cultivation was conducted in a laboratory-scale aerobic bioreactor under controlled conditions (air flow 0.4 L/min, temperature 26 °C, pH 8). The microalgae demonstrated high efficiency in nutrient removal from the wastewater. During the treatment process, the removal efficiencies for chemical oxygen demand (COD) and biological oxygen demand (BOD) reached 93.7% and 98.1%, respectively, while total organic carbon (TOC) decreased by 95.7%. Concentrations of nitrites and nitrates were reduced by 96%, and the most significant reductions among metal ions were observed for calcium (82.7%) and manganese (97.6%) [1].

Reference:

[1] Khakimova, N.; Maravić, N.; Davidović, P.; Blagojević, D.; Bečelić-Tomin, M.; Simeunović, J.; Pešić, V.; Šereš, Z.; Mandić, A.; Pojić, M.; et al.. *Water* 2022, 14(6), 860

Key words: wastewater treatment; microalgae cultivation; biorefinery concept

Acknowledgment: IMPRESS, Grant Agreement ID: 101084437

COST-BENEFIT EVALUATION OF THE ADSORPTION MEDIA EFFICIENCY AT A PILOT PLANT FOR GROUNDWATER TREATMENT

Nenad Grba^{1*}, Vesna Vasić² and Miloš Dubovina³

¹ Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, 21102 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

² Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, 21101 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

³ University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy 11000 Beograd, Republic of Serbia

* nenad.grba@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Groundwater treatment requires cost-effective and technologically reliable solutions capable of removing priority contaminants such as iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), ammonium (NH₄⁺), and organic matter. This Pilot study was conducted at Public Utility Company “Water and Sewerage”, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia as semi-industrial tests in order to evaluate the performance of different adsorption media. Five filter bed configurations were tested in a specially designed Pilot unit consisting of two serially connected gravity columns: first with aeration, filtration and sedimentation processes and second with Granular Activated Carbon (GAC), natural zeolite, and three GAC-zeolite mixtures (ratios 1:1, 3:2, and 2:3). The results showed that pure GAC consistently achieved high removal of Fe and absorbing of organic matter, with average efficiencies above 90% and effluent concentrations well below maximum permissible limits. However, due to its high market cost (8–10 times higher than zeolite), GAC exhibited the lowest economic index (8.0), making it less favorable for resource-limited systems. Zeolite demonstrated the highest average efficiency (96.2%) and the best cost-effectiveness, with an economic index of 68.4. Zeolite excelled in ammonium and manganese reduction (e.g. native 456–653 µg/L to below 50 µg/L prescribed manganese value), particularly when used alone or in a 2:3 mixture. Mixed configurations provided sustainable solutions, with the GAC:zeolite = 2:3 ratio achieving 89.9% average efficiency and an economic index of 18.2. This mixture proved particularly suitable for waters rich in ammonium and manganese, while the 1:1 configuration showed reduced stability in maintaining Fe removal below regulatory thresholds. Research indicate that tailoring adsorbent composition to raw water quality and local economic constraints is essential for ensuring stable, efficient, and affordable drinking water treatment also regarding the most challenging aspects of climate changes.

Key words: Pilot-scale study; Groundwater treatment; Iron, manganese, and ammonium removal; Natural and conventional adsorbents; Cost–benefit analysis

Acknowledgment: “The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No, 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125)” and Public Utility Company “Water and Sewerage”, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia within Pilot Project for Treatment and Analysis of Raw Water within the Pre-treatment System at the Public Utility Company “Water and Sewerage”, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia” (Contract No, 0607-68/24-107 from 26.12.2024).

"FROM WASTE TO RESOURCE" - DANUBEcare

Vesna Vasić^{1*}, Dragana Lukić¹, Ivana Čabarkapa², Slađana Rakita², Jasmina Lazarević²

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Institute of Food Technology in Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

* vesna.vasic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Invasive Alien Species (IAS) are recognized among the top five direct drivers of biodiversity loss and represent a major threat to ecosystems and human well-being in the coming decade. The spiny-cheek crayfish (*Faxonius limosus*), native to Eastern North America, has been reported in over 20 European countries and is listed as an IAS of Union concern. As one of the most significant aquatic invaders in European inland waters, its prevention, control, and eradication remain a major challenge for biodiversity conservation across Europe.

The DANUBEcare project applies an integrated approach to mitigate the negative impact of *F. limosus* on the Danube ecosystem. Its goal is to preserve biodiversity while transforming scientific knowledge into innovative solutions, including the development of food products enriched with crayfish meat, novel biosorbents, and rubber bio-fillers. In doing so, the project promotes the creation of a sustainable, circular economy model. Aligned with its overarching objectives, DANUBEcare will deliver broad, multi-level, and inclusive impacts. Its activities will facilitate knowledge exchange between research institutions, industry, and the wider community, extending their influence to the European level. By combining technological expertise, business-oriented thinking, practical implementation capacity, and strong collaborative networks, the project will create long-lasting benefits for all stakeholders, well beyond its lifetime.

Keywords: *invasive species, biosorbents, biodiversity, food products*

Acknowledgment: *This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No. 7417. Reducing the negative impact of invasive crayfish Faxonius limosus in the Danube by smart exploitation of their meat and shells "DANUBEcare.*

REUSABILITY OF BIOCHAR AS A CATALYST IN PERSULFATE SYSTEMS FOR ATRAZINE AND SIMAZINE DEGRADATION

Tijana Marjanović Srebro¹, Jasmina Anojčić¹, Sanja Mutić¹, Nina Đukanović¹, Tamara Apostolović¹, Sabolč Bognar¹, Jelena Beljin^{1*}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

* jelena.beljin@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

The reusability of biochar (BC) in persulfate (PS) activation remains insufficiently explored, although it is one of the key factors for the potential practical application of this process in wastewater treatment. Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of BC/PS systems for degrading organochlorine pesticides such as lindane and β -endosulfan [1], highlighting the importance of assessing catalyst performance over multiple cycles. Building on this, it is essential to evaluate whether BC can maintain efficiency when applied to other pesticide classes.

In this work, BC prepared at 700 °C from hardwood, corn cob, and wheat straw was tested through five consecutive degradation cycles for the triazine herbicides atrazine and simazine. In previous experiments, degradation efficiencies were monitored for up to 48 h, confirming that equilibrium was reached after 4 h. Based on this, all reusability experiments were conducted within this time frame, with degradation efficiencies determined at 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 h. After each cycle, the recovered BC was rinsed, dried, and reused under identical conditions (100 μ g/L initial pesticide concentration, PS 3.0 mM, BC 0.2 g/L, pH 7.02, 180 rpm).

The results revealed clear differences between the two triazine herbicides. Atrazine removal depended on the BC source: hardwood-derived BC retained >85% degradation efficiency after five cycles (4 h), while corn cob and wheat straw BC showed moderate declines. In contrast, simazine degradation remained consistently >90% across all BC and cycles, showing that simazine maintained stable degradation efficiency in this system over multiple cycles.

These results suggest that both the pesticide type and the BC feedstock significantly influence the reusability of BC/PS systems, in which BC functions as a catalyst, indicating their potential in water treatment.

[1] T. Simetić, T. Marjanović Srebro, T. Apostolović, J. Anojčić, N. Đukanović, S. Mutić, J. Molnar Jazić, J. Beljin, *Processes*, 2025, 13, 1856.

Keywords: water; biochar; advanced oxidation processes

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #10810, Sustainable solutions in environmental chemistry: exploring biochar potential—EnviroChar

EVALUATION OF STABILIZED DREDGED SEDIMENT’S POTENTIAL FOR USE IN SUBGRADE MATERIAL WITH LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

Nataša Slijepčević^{1*}, Dragana Tomašević Pilipović¹, Boris Agarski², Miloš Šešlija², Milana Ilić Mićunović²

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 6, Novi Sad, Serbia

* natasa.slijepcevic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Stabilization/solidification (S/S) treatment processes are widely employed for the remediation of contaminated sediments, aiming to immobilize hazardous substances and reduce environmental risks, for potential further use in construction industry. To comprehensively evaluate the environmental sustainability of these remediation technique, life cycle assessment (LCA) serves as a pivotal tool, analyzing impacts from material extraction through to the end-of-life stages.

This study applies LCA approach to assess the environmental footprint of various S/S treatment strategies. The research investigates different formulations using cement, lime, and alternative binders to immobilize heavy metals effectively. Key environmental indicators, including global warming potential, energy consumption, and resource depletion, are analyzed across all treatment stages—ranging from material extraction to final disposal. Experimental results are integrated into the LCA framework to compare the impacts of different stabilization strategies.

This study underscores the necessity of integrating LCA into the design of sediment remediation technologies, ensuring that treatment processes align with circular economy principles and sustainability goals. The results contribute to a better understanding of the trade-offs between contaminant stabilization and environmental impact, providing valuable insights for scaling up S/S applications in sediment management.

Key words: *sediment; remediation; stabilization; solidification; LCA.*

Acknowledgment: *This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #14859, Evaluation of stabilized dredged sediment’s potential for use in subgrade material with Life Cycle Assessment“, ACRONYM: SedSubMat*

FROM CONTAMINATED SEDIMENTS TO SAFE REUSE: LONG-TERM STABILIZATION AND SOLIDIFICATION

Dunja Rađenović Veselić^{1*}, Dragana Tomašević Pilipović¹, Đurđa Kerkez¹

¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

*dunja.radjenovic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

This study explores the long-term stabilization of metal-contaminated sediment from the Great Bačka Canal using selected immobilizing agents (cement, lime, kaolinite, montmorillonite, zeolite, and fly ash), aiming to support circular economy approaches through potential sediment reuse. Three mixtures were prepared and aged for seven years to evaluate their effectiveness in reducing metal mobility, toxicity, and enhancing mechanical stability. Sequential extraction revealed that the cement-based mixture (C5S95) achieved the lowest metal mobility, with less than 11% of metals in the exchangeable fraction, while mixtures containing montmorillonite-lime (M30L10S60) and kaolinite-fly ash (K5F30S65) retained higher proportions of cadmium and nickel in labile forms, indicating higher environmental risk. Ecotoxicity tests with *Vibrio fischeri* corroborated these findings: C5S95 exhibited minimal inhibition, K30L10S65 moderate, and M30L10S60 the highest. Compressive strength measurements further demonstrated that C5 possessed superior mechanical stability (9 MPa) compared to the other mixtures. Overall, the results highlight the importance of mixture composition for long-term immobilization and environmental safety. Cement-based stabilization not only effectively reduces metal bioavailability and ecotoxicity but also provides sufficient structural integrity, suggesting potential applications in sediment reuse strategies and sustainable construction practices. This work contributes to the development of environmentally responsible sediment management approaches, aligning with circular economy principles and long-term risk mitigation.

Key words: *sediment contamination, metal immobilization, S/S treatment, ecotoxicity, circular economy*

Acknowledgment: *The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125).*

UNDERSTANDING MICROPLASTIC POLLUTION IN AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS AND STRATEGIES FOR REMOVAL THROUGH WATER TREATMENT

Aleksandra Tubić*, Maja Vujić, Sanja Vasiljević

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad -

* aleksandra.tubic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Microplastics represent a global environmental issue due to their detrimental effects on ecosystem quality, biodiversity, and human health. Defined as polymer particles smaller than 5 mm in size, they have been detected in all environmental compartments. Microplastics comprise a diverse group of polymers that vary in shape, color, and size. Their presence in the environment results from inadequate waste management, industrial activities, untreated and treated wastewater discharges, traffic, terrestrial and aquatic tourism, among numerous other sources.

One of the most significant sources of microplastics in aquatic ecosystems is wastewater, whether discharged untreated or originating from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). The most commonly detected polymers in wastewater include polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polystyrene (PS), along with their various modifications. These typically originate from textile fibers, plastic consumer products, tire abrasion residues, and other sources.

Although WWTPs act as barriers in the purification process, they also serve as critical entry points of microplastics into terrestrial and aquatic environments, primarily through sludge disposal and the discharge of treated effluent. Due to this pivotal role, the occurrence and behavior of microplastics in WWTPs have become the subject of intensive scientific investigation. Despite the generally high removal efficiency of WWTPs, complete elimination of microplastics has not yet been achieved.

Consequently, the implementation of tertiary and quaternary treatment processes in WWTPs has been increasingly proposed. These advanced treatment stages involve various technologies, including adsorption, coagulation–flocculation, and membrane filtration, among others. This paper provides an overview of the potential application of such processes for microplastic removal in wastewater treatment.

Key words: *microplastic, wastewater, treatment, aquatic ecosystems*

Acknowledgment: *The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125)*

**TwINSol-CECs: ENHANCING WESTERN BALKAN CAPACITIES FOR EMERGING
CONTAMINANTS MONITORING AND REMOVAL FROM WATER SYSTEMS
TOWARD ZERO POLLUTION**

Nataša Đurišić Mladenović

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

* natasa.mladenovic@uns.ac.rs, natasadjm@tf.uns.ac.rs

Contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) are gaining increasing attention among researchers and policymakers due to their widespread presence in aquatic environments and their potentially harmful effects on ecosystems and human health. Advances in modern analytical instrumentation have made it possible to detect these substances at trace levels in surface, groundwater, wastewater, and even drinking water; however, systematic and regular monitoring schemes are still lacking to reveal their full range of occurrence and to enable assessment of long-term exposure and associated risks. The growing significance of CECs has also been recognized at the regulatory level. This is reflected in the recent provisional political agreement between the Council Presidency and the European Parliament on the proposed directive to revise and update the lists of pollutants affecting surface and groundwater. The agreement introduces updated environmental quality standards for existing pollutants, adds new substances of concern, and aligns EU water policy with the latest scientific evidence. This revision represents a crucial step in safeguarding water quality across Europe by strengthening the framework for combating harmful chemicals, enhancing monitoring systems, and ensuring consistency with river basin management plans that guide the implementation of EU water policy.

In this context, the Horizon Europe Western Balkans Twinning project TwiNSol-CECs aims to enhance the capacities of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, as one of the leading academic institutions in the region, for the monitoring and removal of CECs from water systems, thereby contributing to the EU’s long-term ambition of achieving zero pollution. The project focuses on two major challenges: (1) developing advanced analytical approaches based on LC-MS detection (including LC-HRMS suspect screening and non-target analysis) capable of detecting a wide range of CECs simultaneously in various types of water, and (2) creating innovative and sustainable removal methods (membrane-based, biomaterial- and biochar-based adsorption, and advanced oxidation processes), using non-toxic materials and promoting the valorization of organic matter. By addressing these scientific and technological challenges, TwiNSol-CECs will strengthen regional research excellence in the field of CECs, foster collaboration with leading EU research partners, and contribute to sustainable water management and environmental protection across the Western Balkans.

Key words: *Contaminants of emerging concern, water, advanced analytics, innovative methods*

Acknowledgment: *This study is conducted under the project TwiNSol-CECs which has received funding from the Horizon Europe program under grant agreement No.101059867.*

VALORIZATION OF EFFLUENTS FROM URBAN WASTEWATER TREATMENT BY DEVELOPING BIOPROCESS SOLUTIONS FOR BIOFERTILIZERS AND BIOMATERIALS PRODUCTION

Ivana Danilov^{1*}, Jovana Grahovac¹, Vanja Vlajkov¹, Snežana Vučetić², Bojan Miljević², Vesna Miljić²

¹Department of Biotechnology, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²Department of Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

* ivana.pajcin@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Urban wastewater treatment represents one of the most pressing challenges in modern society, especially considering the disposal of the effluents from wastewater treatment procedures. The relatively novel concept of wastewater treatment includes application of microbial fuel cells (MFCs), using microbial biocatalysts to degrade organic matter and simultaneously produce electricity. Through the precise selection of biocatalysts and careful engineering of the MFC system, the MFC catholyte (the liquid medium from the cathodic chamber) could be tuned to contain sufficient concentrations of NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , and K^+ ions to be further utilized as fertilizer in the hydroponic systems for plant growing. Simultaneously, the MFC-generated electricity could be used to self-power the hydroponics system in terms of lighting, pumps etc. The main effluents of the proposed system comprise solid effluents such as sludge from urban wastewater treatment and hydroponics sludge, as well as liquid effluents such as the excess MFC catholyte and hydroponics waste solution. These effluents could be further valorized in two main directions: (1) as nutrient sources for microorganisms exhibiting plant growth-promoting activity, thus producing both liquid plant biostimulants or solid organic-microbial biofertilizers/soil amendments, or (2) as circular raw materials for production of green building materials (GBMs). The valorization route aimed at GBM production also includes application of microbially induced calcite precipitation (MICP), where liquid effluents could be applied as substrates for growth of bacterial strains capable of calcite precipitation. The current research activities are aimed at isolation and characterization of microbial active components to be used both in biofertilizing products (taking into account the list of allowed microbial active components by the EU Fertilizing Products Regulation, namely nitrogen-fixing bacteria) and in MICP-based design of GBMs. The further research activities will be aimed at development of scalable TRL4 bioprocess solutions and prototypes of biofertilizing products and GBMs based on the presented methodology.

Key words: *microbial fuel cell, hydroponics, sludge, biostimulant, green building material*

Acknowledgment: *This work was financially supported by the Microbial-Hydroponics (Mi-Hy) project, funded by the European Innovation Council (grant no. 101114746).*

ECO-FRIENDLY CONCEPT FOR FRIENDLY CONCEPT FOR THE CONTROL OF INVASIVE STINK BUGS

Tamara Erceg^{1*}, Vanja Travičić¹, Vesna Teofilović¹, Milica Aćimović², Godrana Ćetković²

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad

²Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Novi Sad

* tamara.erceg@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Stink bugs pose a significant threat to both agricultural production and urban households, leading to the widespread use of chemical insecticides with adverse environmental and health effects. The adverse effects of chemical pesticides on human health are of increasing concern, with millions of cases of poisoning and thousands of deaths annually. Additionally, pesticide residues on food products are a significant concern to consumers. To address these challenges, the BugControl project proposes the use of biopesticides derived from natural sources, such as essential oils, in combination with neem oil as a carrier in nanoemulsion formulations. The innovative nanoemulsion formulation is designed to efficiently encapsulate and deliver essential oils to stink bugs, resulting in effective and long-lasting pest control. This reduces the need for frequent reapplication, reducing costs and minimizing environmental impact. Nanoemulsions offer several advantages, such as improved stability, transparency, and reduced residue (visible trace) of the product compared to traditional oil-based formulations. Furthermore, this concept adopts a “green” approach by using biodegradable surfactants and biosurfactants instead of synthetic surfactants to prepare the nanoemulsion, offering biodegradability, low toxicity, reduced environmental impact and a potential contribution to bioremediation efforts, improving the overall sustainability of the repellent formulation that can be precisely applied by spraying on various crops, fruits, vegetables, flowers, trees and household surfaces, providing effective protection against invasive stink bugs, while promoting environmental protection and human health.

Key words: *biopesticide, biodegradable surfactants, nanoemulsions.*

Acknowledgment: *Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, Proof of concept, ECO-FRIENDLY CONCEPT FOR FRIENDLY CONCEPT FOR THE CONTROL OF INVASIVE STINK BUGS.*

NEW ZEOLITE FILTER FOR REMOVAL OF ARSENIC FROM WATER

Ivan Stijepović*, Marija Milanović, Vesna Vasić, Dragana Lukić

University of Novi Sad Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bul. cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

** ivan.stijepovic@uns.ac.rs*

Abstract

Ceramic filters based on synthetic 4A zeolite for water purification were prepared. Highly porous ceramic filter with appropriate amount and size of pores were produced which could be used for the removal of different metal ions and salts from water. The membrane was enhanced with the addition of ferrite particles suitable for the removal of arsenic from water. Methods for obtaining a porous filter matrix with an optimal concentration of impregnated ferrite particles were established and tested for arsenic removal from water. Filtration device is designed and assembled. It contained zeolite based porous membrane and it was suitable for dead-end filtration. Several ground water samples were tested and high activity of the membrane was established. It is planned to prepare a new ceramic composite system based on the zeolite which will utilize geopolymer as a mechanical support and will avoid sintering step.

Key words: *zeolite, membrane, water filtration, arsenic removal*

Acknowledgment: *This study is conducted under the project ZeoFilAs, Proof of Concept no. 14443, funded by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia.*

SESSION I

INNOVATIONS IN WATER AND
WASTEWATER TREATMENT

ALLOPHANE-BENTONITE BASED GEOPOLYMER AS FAST-ACTING ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF MANGANESE IONS FROM WATER

Mirjana Petronijević^{1*}, Sanja Panić¹, Nenad Grba², Jelena Tanasić¹, Laura Ricciotti³, Svetlana Đogo Mračević⁴, Slavića Ražić⁴

¹University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia,

²University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

³University of Campania - Department of Architecture and Industrial Design, Aversa, Italy

⁴University of Belgrade - Faculty of Pharmacy, Belgrade, Serbia

* mirjana.petronijevic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Manganese ions are an essential element necessary for the growth and development of living organisms. These ions can be present in drinking water resources. However, the presence of manganese ions in drinking water in high concentrations is harmful to human health. For this reason, the maximum permissible concentration of manganese ions in drinking water is set by law at a level below 50 µg/L. It is therefore crucial to monitor the presence of manganese and keep its levels in water sources within the legally permitted limits. One of the most effective methods to remove manganese ions from water is adsorption, using different types of adsorbents such as geomaterials. The aim of this research was to investigate the efficiency of geopolymers based on a mixture of allophane and bentonite as adsorbents for the removal of manganese ions from groundwater. The results are compared with the process efficiency of bentonite-based geopolymers and with bentonite alone.

The removal of manganese ions from water was investigated in a batch adsorption test at an adsorbent concentration of 1 g/L and a contact time of 1 hour. Groundwater with a high content of manganese ions (600 µg/L) from the territory of the Republic of Serbia was used for the tests. The manganese ion concentrations were measured using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES). The results show that the use of allophane-bentonite geopolymer achieves a high level of manganese ion removal from groundwater. After 5 minutes of the process, an 88% reduction in manganese ion content is achieved, while the removal efficiency increases slightly over time to 93% (after 1 hour). The use of bentonite-based geopolymers showed a significantly lower efficiency in the removal of manganese ions (from 41% to 66%). However, the use of bentonite achieves a higher efficiency (up to 84%) in the removal of manganese ions compared to bentonite-based polymers. It can be concluded that the synthesized allophane-bentonite-based geopolymers exhibit significant manganese ion removal within a short time, making them competitive, cost-effective adsorption materials.

Key words: water treatment, geopolymer, adsorption, manganese ions

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No 7464, Novel Bio-linked Magnetite/geopolymer Composites in Phenol-containing Wastewater Treatment: Toward Zero-waste Technology - BioCompWaterClean.

INFLUENCE OF MIXING SPEED AND CONTACT TIME ON HYDROXIDE PRECIPITATION OF SELECTED METALS

Halid Junuzović*, Sabina Begić, Amra Selimović, Indira Šestan, Melisa Ahmetović, Ervin Karić
University of Tuzla, Faculty of Technology, Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

*halid.junuzovic@untz.ba

Abstract

The aim of the work was to examine the influence of mixing speed and contact time on the precipitation of Cu(II), Ni(II), Pb(II) and Zn(II) ions individually and in binary mixtures of Cu(II)-Ni(II) and Pb(II)-Zn(II) using NaOH, in concentration of 0.1 mol/L. The results showed that the highest removal efficiency individually for Cu(II), Ni(II), Pb(II) and Zn(II) was 99.991%, 94.047%, 94.334% and 99.359% at 800 rpm, while the highest removal efficiency in the Cu(II)-Ni(II) binary mixture was 96.394% and 95.528% at 100 rpm. Zn(II)-Pb(II) in the binary mixture had the highest removal efficiency of 98.634% 99.293% at 800 rpm. At a contact time of 30 minutes, the highest removal efficiency of 99.993%, 95.477% and 90.043% was achieved individually for Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pb(II), while Zn(II) ion achieved the highest removal efficiency of 99.357% at 15 minutes. In the binary mixture of Cu(II)-Ni(II) ions, the highest removal efficiency for Cu(II) ion was 94.118% at 30 minutes, while for Ni(II) ion it was 94.391% at 15 minutes. However, in the binary mixture of Pb(II)-Zn(II) ions at 15 minutes, the highest removal efficiency of 99.187% and 99.05% was achieved, respectively.

Key words: *mixing speed, contact time, removal efficiency*

SUSTAINABLE GROUNDWATER DECONTAMINATION OF ARSENIC USING A RICE HUSK–IRON OXIDE COMPOSITE AND ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESS

Stella Chatzimichailidou*, Maria Xanthopoulou, Ioannis Katsoyiannis
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki Greece, 54124
* sdchatzim@chem.auth.gr

Abstract

This study explores the removal of both pentavalent [As(V)] and trivalent [As(III)] arsenic from groundwater using a composite material made of iron oxides supported on rice husk biomass. To improve the elimination of As(III), a pre-oxidation step was applied with sodium percarbonate—an inexpensive and eco-friendly oxidizing agent—through a Fenton-like advanced oxidation process (AOP). This pretreatment substantially enhanced overall performance, achieving up to 99% removal of As(III) as shown in Fig.1 & 2.

Figure 1. Arsenic removal at varying pH levels with an initial concentration of 100 ppb.

Figure 2. Arsenic removal at varying pH levels with an initial concentration of 1 ppm.

The present work proposes and evaluates an innovative treatment method that combines the strong adsorption capacity of iron oxides with rice husk—an abundant and low-cost agricultural byproduct—and sodium percarbonate, a more stable reagent alternative to hydrogen peroxide, for the production of hydroxyl radicals.

Key words: water, sodium percarbonate, arsenic, rice husk, Fenton

Acknowledgment: We acknowledge support of this work by the project “Hybrid technologies of smart membranes and novel materials for the removal of hexavalent chromium from water” (YII3TA-0560800) which is implemented under the action “SUB1.1: Clusters of Research Excellence” of the sub-action “Strategy for Excellence in Universities & Innovation” (ID 16289), Greece 2.0 – National Recovery and Resilience Fund and funded by European Union Next Generation EU.

ADSORPTION OF CAFFEINE ON GRANULAR ACTIVATED CARBON AND IN SITU REGENERATION OF THE ADSORBENT BY FENTON-TYPE ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESSES

Andromachi Charizani^{1*}, Natalia Malouchi¹, Konstantinos Plakas², Ioannis Katsoyiannis¹

¹*Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) - Department of Chemistry, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece*

²*Center of Research and Technology – Hellas (CERTH) – Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute (CPERI), 6th km Charilaou-Thermi Road, Thermi, 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece*

* acharizc@chem.auth.gr

Abstract

Emerging organic contaminants (EOCs) in drinking water represent a significant global health challenge and, thus, it requires innovative, sustainable and cost-effective technologies for their removal. Caffeine is an alkaloid found in food, beverages and medicines and is considered as a persistent emerging contaminant in surface and wastewater, due to its high consumption on a global scale. Currently, the most widely applied method for purifying drinking water is adsorption on activated carbon, followed by regeneration of the adsorbent, which has a significant environmental and economic impact [1].

The present study focuses on evaluating the adsorptive performance of activated carbon (AC) for caffeine removal from aqueous solutions. Caffeine standards were added to deionized and tap water samples to evaluate the adsorption capacity of the AC in pure and real water matrices. The study examines the influence of various operating parameters, including equilibrium and kinetic analyses. Particular attention was given to the effect of solution pH and the determination of point of zero charge (PZC) to elucidate the role of surface charge in the adsorption process. Moreover, the influence of the initial caffeine concentration on adsorption capacity was investigated, offering valuable insights into the applicability of activated carbon for the treatment of caffeine-contaminated water systems. The experimental investigation of the sorption of caffeine was followed by the in-situ regeneration of the activated carbon by applying Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) based on the Fenton reagent as an effective and environmentally friendly water treatment method.

Reference: [1] V. C. Sarasidis, K. V. Plakas, and A. J. Karabelas, “A Pilot Study of a Hybrid Process Involving In Situ Regenerated Activated Carbon, Membrane Separation and Advanced Oxidation for Water Pollution Abatement,” *Journal of Chemical Engineering Research Updates*, Dec. 2021, vol. 8, pp. 60–72.

Key words: *Adsorption, Caffeine, Granular activated carbon, Fenton reagent, In-situ regeneration*

Acknowledgment: We acknowledge support of this work by the project “Hybrid technologies of smart membranes and novel materials for the removal of hexavalent chromium from water” (YII3TA-0560800) which is implemented under the action “SUB1.1: Clusters of Research Excellence” of the sub-action “Strategy for Excellence in Universities & Innovation” (ID 16289), Greece 2.0 – National Recovery and Resilience Fund and funded by European Union Next Generation EU.

ADVANCED LAYER-BY-LAYER MODIFIED ULTRAFILTRATION MEMBRANES FOR EFFICIENT CR(VI) REMOVAL FROM WATER

Natalia Malouchi^{1*}, Stella Chatzimichailidou¹, Veroniki Bakola², Olympia Kotrotsiou²,
Konstantinos V. Plakas², Ioannis A. Katsoyiannis¹

¹Laboratory of Chemical and Environmental Technology, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

²Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute, Centre for Research and Technology-Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece

*nmalouchi@chem.auth.gr

Abstract

Hexavalent chromium [Cr(VI)] is a highly toxic contaminant frequently detected in natural and industrial waters, raising serious concerns for environmental and public health protection. Conventional treatment technologies, such as the use of Fe(II) salts for reduction–precipitation, suffer from significant drawbacks, including high chemical demand, production of toxic sludge, and the risk of residual iron in the treated water [1]. Membrane-based processes, such as ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF) and reverse osmosis (RO), have emerged as promising alternatives in recent decades. While they provide high-quality treated water, UF in particular is unable to remove dissolved ions due to its porous structure and molecular weight cut-off characteristics [2].

To overcome these limitations, this study investigates the modification of commercial UF membranes using the Layer-by-Layer (LbL) assembly of oppositely charged polyelectrolytes, stabilized by covalent crosslinking. The modified membranes were characterized in terms of surface morphology, hydrophilicity, and surface charge, and their properties were compared to those of unmodified membranes.

Results showed that the LbL process produced membranes with smoother surfaces and improved hydrophilic characteristics. The impact of the multilayer structure on separation efficiency was also evaluated across different pH values. Experiments specifically targeting Cr(VI) removal demonstrated that the developed membranes outperformed traditional separation materials, confirming their potential for effective treatment of chromium-contaminated water.

This study underlines how innovative membrane modification strategies can bridge laboratory-scale development with field implementation, contributing to safer drinking water supplies. Ongoing work includes pilot-scale validation and cost-benefit analysis to further support real-world application.

[1] Y. Liu, G.Q. Chen, X. Yang, H. Deng, Membranes, 2019, 9, 20.

[2] M. Xanthopoulou, I.A. Katsoyiannis, New Mater. Compd. Appl., 2019, 3, 38–46.

Key words: hexavalent chromium; ultrafiltration; Layer-by-Layer membranes; drinking water; scalability

Acknowledgment: We acknowledge support of this work by the project “Hybrid technologies of smart membranes and novel materials for the removal of hexavalent chromium from water” (YII3TA-0560800) which is implemented under the action “SUB1.1: Clusters of Research Excellence” of the sub-action “Strategy for Excellence in Universities & Innovation” (ID 16289), Greece 2.0 – National Recovery and Resilience Fund and funded by European Union Next Generation EU.

IMPACT OF NATURAL WATER CONSTITUENTS ON THE ADSORPTION OF Cr(VI) BY POLYETHYLENIMINE-MODIFIED SILICA

Maria Xanthopoulou*, Andromachi Charizani, Dimitrios Gkiliopoulos, Konstantinos S. Triantafyllidis, Margaritis Kostoglou, and Ioannis A. Katsoyiannis

Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Chemistry, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece.

* mariaxanth@chem.auth.gr

Abstract

Hexavalent chromium, Cr(VI), is a highly toxic and carcinogenic contaminant frequently detected in natural waters. In previous studies, we demonstrated the high efficiency of polyethylenimine-modified silica (SiO₂-PEI) for Cr(VI) removal under controlled conditions with deionized water [1]. However, natural water matrices contain a variety of coexisting ions that may significantly affect removal performance. In the present study, we investigate the performance of SiO₂-PEI in real natural water samples, focusing on the influence of common competing anionic and cationic species. Batch adsorption experiments were performed to evaluate removal efficiency and material stability under environmentally relevant conditions. The results highlight the robustness of the hybrid adsorbent, while also revealing the extent to which ionic competition and matrix complexity influence Cr(VI) binding. These findings provide a more realistic assessment of the applicability of SiO₂-PEI for Cr(VI) remediation in natural aquatic systems and contribute to the development of effective strategies for water treatment technologies.

Reference:

[1] M. Xanthopoulou, D. Gkiliopoulos, K. S. Triantafyllidis, M. Kostoglou, I. A. Katsoyiannis, *Environ Sci Pollut Res*, 2025, 32, 9443–9461

Key words: *Cr(VI) adsorption, modified silica, polyethylenimine*

Acknowledgment: *We acknowledge support of this work by the project “Hybrid technologies of smart membranes and novel materials for the removal of hexavalent chromium from water” (YΠ3TA-0560800) which is implemented under the action “SUB1.1: Clusters of Research Excellence” of the sub-action “Strategy for Excellence in Universities & Innovation” (ID 16289), Greece 2.0 – National Recovery and Resilience Fund and funded by European Union Next Generation EU.*

APPLICATION OF HYDROCHAR AS ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF FAMOTIDINE FROM WATER

Marija Šobić*, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Igor Antić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

*sobicmarija@gmail.com

Abstract

The presence of pharmaceutically active compounds (such as famotidine) in water resources has become an important environmental concern due to their potential adverse effects on ecosystems and human health. Conventional treatment technologies are often insufficient for their complete elimination, which emphasizes the need for cost-effective and sustainable alternatives. Hydrochar, a carbon-rich material obtained by hydrothermal carbonization of biomass, has recently attracted attention as a promising adsorbent for the removal of organic micropollutants from aqueous systems.

In this study, the adsorption capacity of unmodified waste wood-derived hydrochar was examined for the removal of famotidine from water. Experiments were performed on a model solution of the famotidine (20 µg/L) in deionized water. Adsorption experiments were performed under batch conditions using a hydrochar concentration of 2.0 g/L and a contact time of 120 min. The results showed that 73% of famotidine was removed within the first 30 min, demonstrating that hydrochar can be applied as an effective, low-cost, and environmentally friendly material for famotidine removal. These findings confirm the potential of hydrochar as adsorbent for pharmaceutically active compounds removal from water, with opportunities for further optimization of process conditions.

Key words: *hydrochar, famotidine, adsorption, water treatment*

Acknowledgment: *This study is conducted under the project TwiNSol-CECs which has received funding from the Horizon Europe program under grant agreement No.101059867.*

DEVELOPMENT OF A PILOT UNIT WITH SMART MEMBRANES AND INNOVATIVE ADSORBENT MATERIALS FOR THE REMOVAL OF HEXAVALENT CHROMIUM FROM WATER

Dimitra Karagiannidi, Ourania Epoglou

INTERGEO LTD., Thessaloniki, Greece
dimitra.karagiannidi@intergeo.com

Abstract

The presence of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) in groundwater and surface water is a major environmental and health issue. The European Union Directive (2020/2184) reduces the permissible limit of Cr(VI) in drinking water to 25 µg/L by 2036, making the development of innovative decontamination technologies imperative.

As part of this research, a pilot water treatment unit is being designed and constructed with modified polymer membranes (e.g., polysulfone, polyacrylonitrile), which, through Layer-by-Layer technology and the introduction of polycationic groups (e.g., polyethyleneimine), acquire the ability to bind Cr(VI). Their performance will be evaluated through experiments on contaminated borehole water, taking into account parameters such as stability, regeneration, and maintenance. At the same time, the use of modified activated carbons for Cr(VI) adsorption will be tested in a pilot unit. The ultimate goal is to develop hybrid technology that combines membranes with adsorption to achieve water decontamination with Cr(VI) concentrations below the limits.

An indicative representation of the membrane unit is shown in Figure 8a, while Figure 8b shows the pilot adsorption unit, where the ability of selected modified activated carbons to remove Cr(VI) from contaminated groundwater wells will be investigated.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic representation of a water treatment plant with modified ultrafiltration membranes. (b) Imaging of a pilot water treatment plant with adsorption columns. (c) Hybrid water treatment technology, based on a combination of filtration and adsorption.

Key words: chromium, decontamination, water, treatment, plant

Acknowledgment: We acknowledge support of this work by the project “Hybrid technologies of smart membranes and novel materials for the removal of hexavalent chromium from water” (YII3TA-0560800) which is implemented under the action “SUB1.1: Clusters of Research

BioCompWaterClean Workshop

“New applications in wastewater treatment on the way to zero-waste technology”

20 – 21. October 2025, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

Excellence” of the sub-action “Strategy for Excellence in Universities & Innovation” (ID 16289), Greece 2.0 – National Recovery and Resilience Fund and funded by European Union Next Generation EU.

INTEGRATING FORESTRY RESOURCES INTO WASTEWATER TREATMENT: ADSORPTIVE POTENTIAL OF VARIOUS TREE SPECIES FOR CHROMIUM(VI) REMOVAL

Teodora Subić^{1*}, Dragana Lukić¹, Vesna Vasić¹, Marko Ilić², Srdjan Stojnić², Saša Orlović²

¹University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad – Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Novi Sad, Serbia

* subic.99.19.b@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Forestry residues offer a low-cost, renewable resource for wastewater treatment. Their potential for removing toxic metals, such as hexavalent chromium, aligns with circular economy principles and sustainable environmental management.

This study aimed to evaluate the potential of 13 tree species as natural adsorbents for the removal of hexavalent chromium (Cr^{6+}) ions from contaminated aqueous solutions. The selected species included different broadleaf and coniferous tree species. The aim was not only to assess their adsorption efficiency but also to consider their ecological suitability for broader application.

Batch adsorption experiments were conducted under controlled conditions in model water of 50 mg/l of Cr^{6+} ions and pH 2, with a contact time of 24 hours. Adsorption efficiency was determined using spectrophotometric methods. The results indicate that the adsorption capacity of the investigated biomass ranges from 4.2 to 10.3 mg/g, while the efficiency of Cr (VI) ion removal varies between 41% and 99%. The highest capacity values were recorded for cypress (9.79 mg/g) and white willow (10.3 mg/g), with removal efficiencies of 94% and 99.5%, respectively. Literature data shows that Scots pine timber filings under similar conditions (pH 2.2, dose 3.5 g/L, initial concentration 50 mg/L) adsorb only around 30% of Cr^{6+} [1].

Given the abundance and renewability, the studied materials are attractive candidates for integration into sustainable wastewater treatment technologies. However, further ecological assessment is necessary before large-scale application. Overall, the results contribute to the growing body of research supporting the use of forest biomass in circular economy models and environmentally responsible remediation practices.

[1] A. Mudhoo, P.D. Seenauth, RASAYAN J. Chem., 4, 2011, 56.

Key words: forest residues, adsorption, chromium, wastewater

Acknowledgment: Financial support from the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia (Program No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200134, 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200134 and 451-03-66/2024-03/ 200197).

ADSORPTION OF METOLACHLOR ON WOODCHIPS

Klára Novotná*, Karel Hrich, Jitka Malá

Brno University of Technology, Faculty of Civil Engineering, Institute of Chemistry, Brno, Czech Republic

klara.novotna@vut.cz

Abstract

Denitrifying woodchip bioreactors (DWBs) are utilised for reducing nitrate levels in agricultural runoffs. They typically take the form of excavations filled with woodchips.

Other substances, including pesticides and their metabolites, were also identified at the inlet to the DWBs. Their decomposition times often reaches tens of days. Extending their retention time through adsorption on woodchips could foster their biodegradation.

The hydraulic retention time in DWBs can be up to 24 hours. Therefore, a 24-hour test was designed that allows to determine the adsorption rate of pesticides onto the bioreactor filling.

The adsorption test was carried out with metolachlor as a model compound in 16 two-litre glass bottles. 48 hours before the start of the test, 30 g of poplar shavings and 2 L of liquid medium containing 15 mg NO₃-N/L were added to each bottle. The bottles were bubbled with argon, closed, and incubated at a temperature of 15 °C.

At the start of the experiment, a mixture containing metolachlor and its 4 metabolites was added to each bottle, so that the initial concentration of metolachlor was 0.25 µg/L, and its metabolites 0.5 µg/L. The pH, dissolved oxygen, NO₃-N, and the concentration of pesticide substances were measured. Every 6 hours, the adsorption process was terminated in 4 bottles. The previously mentioned parameters plus COD and NO₂-N concentrations were determined.

During the test period, denitrifying conditions were sustained in the bottles, as evidenced by the low oxygen concentration (<1 mg/L) and the NO₃-N decrease. The average COD was 408 mg/L.

The loss of the pesticide substances increased during the experiment and after 24 hours reached the following values: 60% metolachlor NOA 413173, 32% metolachlor CGA 368208, 25% metolachlor, 18% metolachlor ESA and 15% metolachlor OA.

Key words: *Denitrifying woodchip bioreactor, denitrification, pesticide, laboratory adsorption test*

Acknowledgment: *Funding for project SS06020006 was provided by Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.*

MIXED OXIDES AS PHOTOCATALYSTS FOR DEGRADATION OF BINARY DYE SYSTEMS IN WATER SOLUTIONS

Đurđica Karanović*, Milica Hadnađev-Kostić, Tatjana Vulić

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

* djurdjicakaranovic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Azo dyes are extensively used in various industries and are frequently detected in wastewater due to their high stability and resistance to conventional treatment methods. Mixed oxides derived from layered double hydroxides (LDHs) have been recognized as efficient photocatalysts for the degradation of organic pollutants due to their textural properties and structural versatility. This study investigates the performance of ZnCr-LDH-derived mixed oxides thermally treated at 700 and 900 °C in the simultaneous photocatalytic degradation of two azo dyes (Rhodamine B and Methylene Blue) from aqueous solution. The structural analysis (XRD) of ZnCr-700 and ZnCr-900 photocatalysts revealed the presence of the dominant ZnO phase and the spinel ZnCr₂O₄ phase. Higher thermal treatment temperature, sample ZnCr-900, induced more intense reflections indicating higher crystallinity of the detected phases. Textural analysis showed a low amount of adsorbed gas and low BET surface area (16.1 for ZnCr-700 and 4.6 m² g⁻¹ for ZnCr-900), due to the presence of large mesopores in the samples. In single dye systems, the degradation efficiency of Methylene Blue reached 100% for ZnCr-900 and 88% for ZnCr-700, while for Rhodamine B it was 60% and 48%, respectively. In binary dye systems, photocatalytic tests showed high removal efficiency of Methylene Blue (85% for ZnCr-900 and 64% for ZnCr-700 after 7 h). However, the removal efficiency of Rhodamine B was significantly lower (40% for ZnCr-900 and 22% for ZnCr-700 after 7h). The higher efficiency of ZnCr-900 could be attributed to its higher crystallinity and the greater amount of photocatalytic active phases. Since both samples exhibited low BET surface areas, it can be concluded that photocatalytic dye degradation in this study was governed mainly by structural properties. The lower Rhodamine B removal efficiency could be explained by hindered adsorption on active sites, due to its high stability and relatively large molecular size. Overall, both materials demonstrate strong potential for future applications in wastewater purification.

Key words: wastewater remediation, photocatalysis, azo dyes

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200134).

MAGNETIC BIOCHAR FOR WATER TREATMENT: A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO Cr(VI) REMOVAL

Jasmina Nikić*, Marko Šolić, Jovana Pešić Bajić, Jovana Jokić Govedarica,

Malcolm Watson, Jasmina Agbaba

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

* jasmina.nikic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Heavy metal contamination of water remains a critical environmental and health concern, highlighting the need for efficient and sustainable treatment technologies. Biochar derived from agricultural residues has emerged as a cost-effective adsorbent, and its modification with magnetic nanoparticles offers the added benefit of simple separation and reuse [1]. In this study, magnetic biochar (MBC) was synthesized and evaluated for the removal of chromium (Cr(VI)) from water under batch conditions. Adsorption kinetics were well described by both the pseudo-second-order ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.981$) and Elovich ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.965$) models, indicating a chemisorption-controlled rate-limiting step consistent with an energetically heterogeneous surface and an exponentially decreasing adsorption rate. Equilibrium data were best represented by the Freundlich isotherm ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.987$), confirming heterogeneous multilayer adsorption, while the Langmuir model ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.970$) suggested a maximum monolayer capacity of 6.60 mg/g. By contrast, the Dubinin–Radushkevich ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.857$) and Temkin ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.814$) models showed poor correlation ($R_{adj}^2 \leq 0.90$) and were excluded from mechanistic interpretation. FTIR spectra confirmed the involvement of oxygenated functional groups and magnetic oxide sites in Cr(VI) uptake. Integrating spectroscopic evidence with kinetic and isotherm modeling, the adsorption mechanism was attributed to a redox–complexation pathway: Cr(VI), present as chromate and hydrogen chromate at neutral pH, is reduced on biochar/oxide surfaces to Cr(III), which subsequently forms strong inner-sphere complexes with hydroxyl and oxide groups. Overall, MBC demonstrates high efficiency and sustainability as an adsorbent for Cr(VI) removal. Future work should assess its regeneration and long-term stability, employ advanced spectroscopic tools to better resolve Cr transformation, and validate performance under continuous-flow and pilot-scale conditions to support practical application.

[1] R. Juturu, R. Selvaraj, V.R. Murty, JWPE, 2024, 66, 105908.

Key words: *water, magnetic biochar, heavy metals, isotherm and kinetic modeling, sustainability*

Acknowledgment: *The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125).*

VALORIZATION OF RED MUD AS CATALYST IN FENTON SYSTEMS

Nebojša Vasiljević^{1,2*}, Sanja Panić², Mirjana Petronijević², Nataša Đurišić Mladenović²

¹University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of Technology Zvornik, Zvornik, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

* nebojsa.vasiljevic@tfzv.ues.rs.ba

Abstract

Red mud is industrial waste that is produced in Bayer's process of obtaining aluminum from bauxite ore. It contains more than 50% Fe₂O₃, and therefore represents a cheap source of iron for heterogeneous Fenton processes. This work aims to examine the use of raw red mud in Fenton processes, and the possibility of its transformation into Fenton, photo-Fenton, and electro-Fenton catalysts, using methods such as carbothermal reduction, co-pyrolysis with biochar, and supporting on reduced graphene oxide (rGO). Particularly promising are approaches in which red mud is electrochemically activated or doped with metals (e.g., Sn, Co, Ce). Due to such modifications, the availability of Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ centers increases and accelerates the creation of various reactive oxygen species ([•]OH, ¹O₂, [•]O₂⁻), which in model systems led to the rapid removal of phenols, antibiotics, and dyes (90–99%). The results indicate that red mud can be used as a catalyst for application in advanced oxidation processes of wastewater treatment.

Key words: advanced oxidation processes, biochar, fenton, red mud, wastewater treatment

Acknowledgement: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (451-03-136/2025-03/200134 and 451-03-137/2025-03/200134).

PYROPHYLLITE SCHIST – A NATURAL PURIFIER FOR ZINC REMOVAL FROM WATER

Vladimir Šaraba^{1*}, Dajana Lazarević¹, Jelena Jovanović¹, Ivana Jovanić², Tatjana Trtić-Petrović¹

¹University of Belgrade, Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Laboratory of Physics, Belgrade, Serbia

²Geological Survey of Serbia, Chemical Laboratory with Sample Preparation, Belgrade, Serbia

*vladimir.saraba@vin.bg.ac.rs

Abstract

The preservation of clean water resources represents one of the most pressing global challenges of 21st century. The conservation of clean water resources is one of the most significant demands of our time. Since toxic metals can contaminate water supplies and pose serious risks to both humans and ecosystems, the goal is to protect and purify water resources using safe, eco-friendly remediation methods that rely entirely on natural materials and do not produce harmful by products. In this study, we used pyrophyllite schist, a natural geological material obtained from the Parsovići mine in Bosnia and Herzegovina, to evaluate its effectiveness in removing zinc (Zn) from an alkaline water sample (pH 9.6) collected in Bor, Serbia. After a 2-hour contact time, pyrophyllite schist achieved a Zn removal efficiency of 88.1%, indicating a rapid initial sorption process. Prolonging the treatment to 4 hours further enhanced the performance, with removal efficiencies surpassing 90.5%. This progressive increase suggests that extended interaction facilitates additional sorption or diffusion processes within the mineral structure, ultimately leading to near-complete removal of Zn from the alkaline solution. The results confirm that pyrophyllite schist is a highly efficient natural material for the removal of Zn from water, demonstrating its strong potential as a sustainable remediation agent. Further investigations are required to evaluate its long-term performance, regeneration capacity, and applicability under diverse environmental conditions. Such studies will be essential to fully establish its role in large-scale water remediation.

Key words: remediation; green chemistry; clay; sorption; clean water.

Acknowledgment: This work was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (grant agreements No: 451-03-136/2025-03/200017) and project Eco-Friendly Hydrometallurgy for Rare Earths Recycling, FREECOVER (101182579). Also, we are grateful to AD HARBI d.o.o., Sarajevo for the pyrophyllite schist sample, and Mr. Dejan Soldatović from the Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, for collecting the water sample in Bor.

SUSTAINABLE POLLUTANT REMOVAL AND RESOURCE RECOVERY USING MICROALGAE *TETRADESMUS OBLIQUUS* FROM THE TRANS-HIMALAYAN REGION: A CIRCULAR ECONOMY APPROACH

Kriti Sharma, Ashok Kumar Nadda*

Department of Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, Jaypee University of Information Technology,
Waknaghat, Solan, Himachal Pradesh, India

* ashok.nadda09@gmail.com

Abstract

Microalgae have emerged as a promising tool for environmental remediation due to their ability to assimilate pollutants and produce valuable biomass. This study focuses on *Tetradismus obliquus*, a microalgal species isolated from the Trans-Himalayan region, employed for the removal of pollutants from water. The unique resilience of *T. obliquus* to extreme environmental conditions makes it an effective agent for treating contaminated effluents. Post-treatment, the harvested microalgal biomass is valorised for the synthesis of eco-friendly bio-based sponges. These sponges exhibit high porosity and adsorption efficiency, enabling them to further remove pollutants and have other multiple functions in industries. The integration of pollutant removal, biomass valorization, and effluent reuse represents a circular economy model characterized by zero waste generation. This approach not only addresses environmental pollution but also creates value-added products from waste biomass, thereby contributing to sustainable resource management and environmental protection. The findings underscore the potential of microalgae-based systems for scalable and eco-friendly pollutant remediation, particularly in regions facing water scarcity and environmental stress.

Key words: Microalgae, *T. obliquus*, pollutant, remediation, sponge

Acknowledgment: The infrastructure, support, and facilities from the Jaypee University of Information Technology, Waknaghat, Solan are thankfully acknowledged.

SUSTAINABLE WASTEWATER TREATMENT: UTILIZATION OF BIO-WASTE IN LEAD AND COPPER REMOVAL

Nataša Gajić^{1*}, Dragana Radovanović¹, Marija Štulović¹

¹ *Innovation Center of the Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade Ltd, University of Belgrade, Karnegijeva 4, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia*

* ngajic@tmf.bg.ac.rs

Abstract

The increasing demand for low-cost and sustainable adsorbents in wastewater treatment has aimed attention to agricultural bio-waste, which provides an abundant, renewable, and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional materials. Among various types of agricultural bio-waste, plum stones represent a promising but still less explored adsorbent, especially in regions with high fruit processing output, such as Serbia. Nevertheless, their practical application requires pre-treatment to enhance adsorption efficiency. High-energy ball milling applied to waste plum stones successfully enhanced its adsorption capacity by reducing particle size, increasing surface area, and exposing functional groups—without any chemical or thermal modification. The resulting samples were characterized by XRD, FTIR, SEM, and particle size distribution analyses. Milling parameters significantly influenced the morphology and surface chemistry, with optimized conditions (500 rpm, 1 h, 20:1 bpr) yielding the highest adsorption efficiencies of 97% for Pb^{2+} and 52% for Cu^{2+} . The results demonstrate that optimized mechanical activation can convert waste plum stones into effective adsorbents for wastewater treatment, with potential for further applications in environmental remediation.

Key words: *bio-waste, high-energy ball milling, Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} adsorption*

Acknowledgment: *This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Contract No. 451-03-136/2025-03/200287).*

METAGENOMIC INSIGHTS INTO MICROBIAL COMMUNITIES DRIVING NITROGEN AND PHOSPHORUS REMOVAL IN CONSTRUCTED WETLANDS

Milan Glišić*, Ljiljana Tanasić

*Academy of Applied Studies Šabac, Unit for Agricultural and Business Studies and Tourism,
Šabac, Serbia*

* m.glisic@akademijasabac.edu.rs

Abstract

Constructed wetlands (CWs) represent an ecologically sustainable technology for wastewater treatment, particularly effective in the removal of nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), the two key drivers of eutrophication. The efficiency of these systems largely depends on the activity and diversity of microbial communities inhabiting plant rhizospheres, biofilms, and sediments. Recent advances in metagenomic approaches have enabled comprehensive insights into the taxonomic composition and functional potential of these microbial consortia, moving beyond the limitations of cultivation-based methods. This review summarizes current knowledge on microbial taxa and functional genes involved in nitrification, denitrification, anammox, and polyphosphate accumulation in CWs. Special attention is given to ecological interactions among microorganisms, their synergistic relationships with macrophytes, and the influence of environmental factors on microbial community dynamics. Furthermore, the paper discusses how metagenomic insights can be translated into practical improvements in CW design, monitoring, and operation, thereby supporting the development of zero-waste technologies and integration into circular bioeconomy concepts. Future perspectives highlight the need for multi-omics approaches and the application of microbial ecology principles in optimizing CW performance.

Key words: *constructed wetlands, metagenomics, microbial ecology, zero-waste, wastewater treatment*

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE AND PERSPECTIVES OF IMPROVING THE TREATMENT OF WASTEWATER FROM DAIRIES IN SERBIA

Mirhad Bošnjaković¹, Milan Glišić², Jelena Robinić², Ljiljana Tanasić²

¹Faculty of Technical Sciences Brčko, University "Privredna Academy" Brčko, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²The Academy of Applied Studies Šabac, Department of Agricultural Business Studies and Tourism Serbia

e-mail: lj.tanasic@akademijasabac.edu.rs

Abstract

In this work monitored the quality of wastewater in six dairies located in Vojvodina and western Serbia, which cover a wide range of products (milk, yogurt, sour cream, cheese and fermented milk products) in their production program. The samples were analyzed based on key parameters, including pH, BOD₅, COD, total suspended solids, fat, total nitrogen and total phosphorus.

Wastewater samples were analyzed in accordance with domestic and international standards (SRPS EN ISO and EU Directives on industrial wastewater). The results indicated significant variations depending on the production capacity and technological process of the dairies, as well as the level of implementation of the environmental protection system. Wastewater from dairies in Vojvodina showed lower average values of BOD₅ (1.500–2.200 mg O₂/L) and COD (3.000–4.500 mg O₂/L) compared to those in Western Serbia (BOD₅: 2.500–3.500 mg O₂/L; COD: 4.500–6.000 mg O₂/L). Higher concentrations of suspended solids, fat, nitrogen and phosphorus were also recorded in dairies in Western Serbia, reflecting the lack of adequate pre-treatment systems.

A comparison of the results between dairies in Vojvodina and Western Serbia shows that dairies in Vojvodina are more technologically advanced and partially implement wastewater pre-treatment, while dairies in Western Serbia are generally of smaller capacity and with higher loads in terms of organic matter and nutrients. These differences clearly indicate the need for a systematic approach to introducing measures to improve wastewater management.

The research results indicate an urgent need for the implementation of advanced wastewater treatment technologies in Serbian dairies, from fat separators and neutralization to biological treatments and membrane bioreactors. Investments in wastewater management are not only environmentally necessary but also economically beneficial, as international studies suggest that every euro invested can generate multiple economic returns through reduced operating costs and improved efficiency.

Key words: Dairy industry, wastewater, BOD₅, COD, treatment technologies.

METHODOLOGY PROPOSALS FOR LONG-TERM MONITORING OF HIGHLY POLLUTED WATER BODIES

Radivoj Tomić^{1*}, Nenad Grba¹, Višnja Mihajlović² and Slaven Tenodi¹

¹ Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad, 21102 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

² University of Novi Sad, Technical Faculty Mihajlo Pupin, 23000, Zrenjanin, Republic of Serbia

* radivoj.tomic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

A recent assessment of the Krivaja River reported extreme exceedances of national standards: Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) by 43×, 5-day Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD₅) by 76×, total nitrogen by 23×, and ammonium (NH₄-N) by 211×—with nickel concentrations above Environmental Quality Standards defined by EU Directive 2013/39/EU [1]. These findings motivate a rigorous, data-driven framework for designing long-term monitoring programs in highly impacted water bodies. We propose a practical pipeline that integrates regulatory exceedance analysis, multivariate statistics, and predictive modeling to (i) identify priority pollutants, (ii) reduce redundancy in indicator sets, and (iii) support targeted interventions and technology choices on the path to zero-waste solutions. The steps are: (1) data curation and normalization, followed by exceedance profiling against national/EU thresholds; (2) correlation screening to remove collinear variables; (3) source-oriented multivariate analysis—principal component analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction and source fingerprints; hierarchical clustering to group sites/periods; and discriminant analysis to test separations; (4) supervised modeling (e.g., Random Forest, LASSO) to rank variables by predictive importance for high-risk states; and (5) composite indicators (water quality index (WQI), pollution load index (PLI), and Nemerow Index) to synthesize risk and support communication with practitioners and policymakers. Applied to the Krivaja case, the framework operationalizes previously reported exceedances and flags metals (e.g., Ni) and nutrient/organic loads as priority targets for routine monitoring and source control. The outcome is a transparent basis for optimizing sampling frequency and station layout, aligning monitoring with best available techniques (BAT) selection, and informing circular/resource-recovery measures consistent with zero-waste objectives.

[1] R. Tomić, N., Grba, V., Mihajlović, B., Dalmacija, M., Bečelić-Tomin, S., Marković and S., Tenodi. "Complex multivariate water quality impact assessment on Krivaja River" *Open Geosciences*, 2025, 17, 20250879. <https://doi.org/10.1515/geo-2025-0879>

Key words: *water quality assessment, river pollution, wastewater impact, multivariate analysis, long-term monitoring*

Acknowledgment: *The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/200125 and 451-03-136/2025-03/200125).*

TARGET ANALYSIS OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN IN SURFACE WATER OF THE GREAT BAČKA CANAL

Dušan Rakić*, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

* rakic.11.20.d@uns.ac.rs

Municipal and industrial wastewater discharges are the primary pathways through which contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) enter aquatic systems. In areas with highly developed agriculture, such as the Vojvodina region, the use of surface water for irrigation raises concerns due to the potential presence of CECs.

This study aims to quantify CECs in the Great Bačka Canal using target analysis of preselected list of compounds. The target CECs were selected based on previously conducted suspected screening analysis (SSA) using high resolution mass spectrometry. A total of 120 grab samples of surface water were collected along the entire length of the canal during three campaigns (spring, summer and autumn in 2024). Sample preparation was conducted using solid-phase extraction (SPE) with a custom-made multi-sorbent cartridge consisting of 200 mg of Oasis HLB sorbent in the upper, and a mixture of 150 mg of Bond Elut PPL, 100 mg of WAX, and 100 mg of WCX in the lower layer. Prior to instrumental analysis, internal standard mixture (40 ng/mL) was added to the final extract.

Target analysis was performed on ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (Accela™ system, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) coupled to triple-quadrupole mass spectrometry (MS/MS) (TSQ Vantage, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) equipped with a heated electrospray ionization source (HESI-II, Thermo Scientific, USA). The Waters Acquity HSS T3 (C18) column (100×2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm particle size) was used for chromatographic separation.

Among the 30 detected compounds, pharmaceuticals (16 compounds) and pesticide residues (7 compounds) were the most common. They were followed by pharmaceuticals transformation products, hormones and sweeteners with 2 compounds each and one industrial chemical. Across all analyzed samples, the concentrations of identified CECs ranged from below the detection limit to 955 ng/L, with overall median and mean values of 28.80 ng/L and 8.39 ng/L, respectively.

Key words: *Contaminants of emerging concern, surface water, solid phase extraction, UHPLC-MS/MS, target analysis*

Acknowledgment: *Acknowledgement - This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No. 7335, Sustainable environmental monitoring and prediction of pollutants spread - EnviLife.*

ORGANIC PRODUCTION IN ORDER TO CONSERVE WATER

Stefan Marković*, Nenad Pavlović, Nemanja Stošić, Vera Rašković

Academy of Applied studies Šabac, Department for Agricultural and Business studies and Tourism

* s.markovic@akademijasabac.edu.rs

Abstract

Water is a precious resource essential for all life, and its conservation has become increasingly crucial in the face of climate change and growing agricultural demands. Organic production, a method that emphasizes sustainability and minimal chemical inputs, plays a significant role in conserving water and promoting efficient water use. The aim of this research is to determine, by reviewing data in scientific literature, in which ways organic production affects water conservation. Organic production is based on principles that prioritize environmental health, biodiversity, and soil fertility. Unlike conventional production, which often relies on synthetic chemicals and intensive irrigation, organic production focuses on natural processes and sustainable practices. One of the core practices in organic production is the use of organic matter, such as compost, green manures, and cover crops. These materials improve soil structure by increasing its organic content and enhancing its water-holding capacity. Organic production promotes the use of mulches and organic amendments, which help retain soil moisture. Mulching with organic materials like straw, leaves, or wood chips creates a protective layer on the soil surface. This layer reduces evaporation, keeps the soil cooler, and maintains moisture levels. As a result, plants receive a consistent supply of water, reducing the reliance on supplemental irrigation. Organic production avoids the use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, which can contribute to water pollution through runoff. Organic farmers often adopt more efficient irrigation practices, such as drip irrigation and rainwater harvesting. Drip irrigation delivers water directly to the plant roots, minimizing water waste and evaporation.

Keywords: *Organic production, water conservation, sustainability, environmental health*

APPLICATION OF HYDROPHOBIC NATURAL DEEP EUTECTIC SOLVENTS FOR ORGANIC MICROPOLLUTANTS REMOVAL FROM WATER –WaDES project

Mirjana Petronijević^{1*}, Sanja Panić¹, Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić¹, Biljana Lončar¹, Jelena Živančev¹, Igor Antić¹, Dušan Rakić¹, Nenad Grba², Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović¹

¹University of Novi Sad Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia,

²University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

* mirjana.petronijevic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Ensuring safe and sustainable water resources is a major challenge of modern society due to the presence of organic micropollutants such as pesticides, pharmaceuticals, endocrine-disrupting compounds, phenols, and perfluorinated substances. These compounds, although often detected in trace concentrations (ng/L–μg/L), pose significant risks to both environmental and human health, while current wastewater treatment plants remain inefficient in their removal. In response to this challenge, the WaDES project proposes the application of natural deep eutectic solvents (NADESs) as environmentally benign extractants for the removal of organic micropollutants from aqueous systems.

NADESs are obtained by mixing naturally derived and biodegradable components such as menthol, camphor, and organic acids, forming novel chemical entities which exhibit several advantages over conventional organic solvents, including low toxicity, biodegradability, easy preparation from inexpensive raw materials, high purity, and hydrophobicity that facilitates simple phase separation from aqueous matrices. Within the WaDES project, innovative hydrophobic NADESs were synthesized and applied for simultaneous removal of 38 representative micropollutants, including pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and perfluorinated compounds, from model water matrices. The extraction process, carried out via liquid–liquid extraction, demonstrated high removal efficiencies, with overall pollutant elimination reaching 98.4%. These results confirm that NADESs based on terpenoids and organic acids represent a promising, green, and cost-effective alternative for the removal of hazardous organic micropollutants from water. The demonstrated high efficiency, environmental compatibility, and simplicity of application highlight their potential for further development and future implementation in industrial and municipal water treatment systems.

Key words: *Natural deep eutectic solvents (NADES), organic micropollutants, extraction, water treatment*

Acknowledgment: *This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No 14144, Hydrophobic deep eutectic solvents as a tool for organic micropollutants removal from water - WaDES.*

SESSION II

PROCESSES SUITABLE FOR
ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS AS A DECISION-SUPPORT TOOL FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF INNOVATIVE CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS

Jovana Topalić^{1*}, Slavica Ražić²

¹University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Technical Sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Belgrade – Faculty of Pharmacy, Belgrade, Serbia

* jovanatopalic90@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

The introduction of innovative materials in the construction industry requires careful evaluation to ensure their economic viability and long-term performance. Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) offers a structured framework for comparing new materials with conventional alternatives by quantifying key parameters such as production cost, service life, energy consumption, and maintenance requirements [1,2]. Beyond economic efficiency, CBA can also incorporate environmental and regulatory considerations, supporting more informed and sustainable material selection.

This paper discusses the potential of CBA as a practical tool in early-stage assessment of novel construction solutions. By identifying relevant input parameters and outlining methodological steps, the aim is to demonstrate how CBA can guide decision-making in material development and application, particularly in contexts where performance, sustainability, and cost must be balanced.

Reference:

[1] A. Unni, G. Anjali, Cost-benefit analysis of conventional and modern building materials for sustainable development of social housing, *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2022, 51407-420.

[2] S. Vedartham, J.S. Sudarsan, V. Narayan, K. Prasanna, S. Mohanakrishna, Cost–Benefit Analysis of Adoption of Green Materials in Conventional Building to Improve Green Rating, *Sustainable Innovations in Construction Management*, 2023, 388, 317-324

Key words: *cost-benefit, analysis, construction, materials*

Acknowledgment: *This research has been supported by the The Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT № 7464 – Novel Bio-linked Magnetite/geopolymer Composites in Phenol-containing Wastewater Treatment: Toward Zero-waste Technology, “BioCompWaterClean” and the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation through Contract No. 451-03-136/2025-03/200156.*

MICROBIAL-ASSISTED PHYTOREMEDIATION STRATEGIES FOR HEAVY METAL REMOVAL FROM POLLUTED SOILS

Jelena Beljin¹, Nina Đukanović¹, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski¹, Dragana Tamindžija¹, Stanko Milić², Tijana Zeremski², Snežana Maletić^{1*}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, 21000 Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

²Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops Novi Sad, Novi Sad, 21000, Serbia

* snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Phytoremediation is an eco-friendly and cost-effective approach that uses plants and their associated microbes to remove, stabilize, or degrade contaminants in soil. It offers a sustainable alternative to conventional remediation methods by harnessing natural processes to restore polluted environments. Its importance lies in minimizing environmental impact while improving soil health and enabling the reclamation of contaminated lands for future use. This study investigates the phytoremediation potential of plants combined with microbial inoculants to mitigate selected heavy metal contamination in soils affected by industrial and anthropogenic activities. Pot experiments were conducted using hemp and sorghum planted in soils with elevated concentrations of chromium (Cr), copper (Cu) and zinc (Zn), originating from contaminated sites including dredged sediment deposits. Microbial amendments, consisting of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) and fungi, were applied to enhance metal bioavailability and uptake. Results revealed that hemp exhibited higher accumulation of Cu and Cr compared to sorghum, particularly when combined with bacterial PGPR treatments, which effectively reduced Zn levels in soil. Sequential extraction analyses indicated that Cr was retained in stable soil fractions, while Zn and Cu demonstrated higher mobility and bioavailability, which were influenced by microbial activity. Leaching tests classified metal leachates as inert, suggesting low environmental risk under current conditions. Microbial inoculants promoted plant growth primarily in less metal-stressed soils, with limited impact under high metal contamination. Overall, this research highlights hemp's superior phytoremediation capacity for key heavy metals and underscores the role of tailored plant–microbe interactions in enhancing remediation efficiency. These findings provide a foundation for optimizing integrated phytoremediation strategies to remediate heavy metal-contaminated soils.

Keywords: Heavy metals, Soil, Remediation, Phytoremediation, Plant

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, #GRANT No 6769, Natural based efficient solution for remediation and revitalization of contaminated locations using energy crops – ReNBES

WASTEWATER AS A SOURCE OF POLYHYDROXYALKANOATES

Dragana Žmukic^{1*}, Anita Leovac Maćerak¹, Đurđa Kerkez¹, Tamara Erceg²

¹University of Novi Sad -Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad- Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia

* dragana.zmukic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) are biopolymers synthesized by various Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria in conditions of excess carbon and limited nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus, they are stored in the form of granules as a reserve of carbon and energy. PHAs are defined based on the length of carbon chain, short (C3-C5), medium (C6-C14) and long (C15 and higher). Biodegradable polymers can be produced from different organic substrates, such as wastewater from different sources which contains organic matter such as sugars, volatile fatty acids, lipids, represent a promising renewable source of bioplastics [1]. The production of PHA from waste streams and wastewater, involves several processes: acidogenic fermentation for the production of volatile fatty acids, enrichment of biomass for the purpose of PHA accumulation and polymer recovery. In short, the production of PHA from wastewater involves the step of selection, accumulation and extraction of PHA [2]. The selection is carried out under feast/famine conditions. The feast/famine process operates by alternating cycles of excess and limiting nutrients, primarily carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus, in the wastewater treatment system. The feast period is characterized by abundance of nutrient and microbial growth. While in the period of famine, the use of stored compounds and reserves for growth is encouraged. PHA is extracted from the enriched biomass. The extraction steps can be different, most often they are performed using chlorine-based solvents, which have been shown to be most effective in the production of PHA. However, considering the toxicity of chlorine-based compounds, new technologies should be used less harmful solvents. The produced biodegradable PHAs represent a promising substitute for fossil-based plastics finding potential application in packing materials.

[1] V. Ahuja, P. Kumar Singh, C. Mahata, J-M. Jeon, G. Kumar, Y-H. Yang, S. Kant Bahatia, *Microbial Cell Factories*, 2024, 23, 187.

[2] G. Mannina, D. Presti, G. Montiel-Jarillo, M. E. Suarez-Ojeda, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2019, 282, 361-369.

Key words: wastewater, polyhydroxyalkanoates, extraction

Acknowledgment: The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125).

BIOREMEDIATION OF LEACHATE FROM MUNICIPAL SOLID WASTE LANDFILLS

Vedran Stuhli*, Alma Huremović, Mirnesa Čorbić, Hana Alihodžić, Maida Smajlović, Ljilja Bojanović

University of Tuzla, Faculty of Technology, Department of Environmental Protection Engineering, Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

* vedran.stuhli@untz.ba

Abstract

Municipal waste management is one of the key environmental challenges in Bosnia and Herzegovina, where landfilling still represents the dominant method of final disposal. Although economically feasible, landfilling generates significant environmental risks, primarily through the emission of landfill gases and the formation of leachate. The treatment of leachate has emerged as a critical point in protecting the environment and public health.

The aim of this study is the laboratory evaluation of biological methods for the treatment of raw leachate from the “Desetine” landfill. The methodological approach encompassed a series of experimental procedures, including the application of various aerobic and anaerobic biological processes. By analyzing parameters such as chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), pH, concentrations of nitrogen compounds, and other specific indicators, the efficiency of the applied methods in reducing pollutant loads was assessed.

The results showed that biological treatments have considerable potential for improving leachate quality, with flexibility for application under the specific conditions of landfills in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The results provide a scientific basis for the further development and implementation of more sustainable and environmentally acceptable systems for landfill leachate management.

Key words: *municipal waste; leachate; landfills; biological treatment; aerobic processes; anaerobic processes*

USE OF WASTEWATER SLUDGE AND OTHER WATER TREATMENT BY-PRODUCTS IN MORTAR AND CONCRETE PRODUCTION

Marina Škondrić^{1*}, Aleksandar Savić¹, Aleksandar Radević¹

¹University of Belgrade Faculty of Civil Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia

* amarina@imk.grf.bg.ac.rs

Abstract

The civil engineering industry is considered to be one of the biggest consumers of natural goods, and therefore is obliged to comply with sustainable development principles. One of the paths taken is the usage of different waste and recycled materials as partial replacement of cement and natural aggregates in mortar and concrete mixtures.

One of the industry by-products whose production is increasing each year is, in fact a range of materials known by the common name “wastewater sludge”. These by-product properties, varying in different types of industries, are greatly dependent on the processes applied during their treatment. Its chemical and mineralogical composition, as well as grain size distribution, will determine the possibilities of its application.

Additional treatments of wastewater sludge are also applied, such as burning and solidification. In the case of solidification, the wastewater sludge is dried and treated with additives based on calcium-oxide and calcium-hydroxide, which results into the production of inert material that can be treated as nonhazardous waste.

In this study, solidified wastewater treated sludge (SWS) was used as partial mass replacement of cement in cement mortar mixtures and pervious concrete pavers in the amount of 10%, 20% and 30%. SWS used had 90% of particles smaller than 160 μm that mainly consisted of CaO (71,7%), while the amounts of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ were lower than 1%.

The results show that the addition of up to 10% of SWS as a partial mass replacement of cement leads to decrease in mechanical properties (compressive and flexural strength) of more than 20%, while higher replacement percentage is not recommended, due to a substantial reduction in strength.

Key words: *solidified wastewater sludge, sustainable development, partial replacement of cement*

Acknowledgment: *This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, 7737365, Zero-Waste Concept for Flood Resilient Cities-Ø-Waste-Water and by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia (grant number 200092).*

***Euphorbia macroclada* BOISS: PHYTOCHEMISTRY AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES**

Sengul Uysal^{1,2*}, Gokhan Zengin³, Ugur Cakilcioglu⁴, Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić⁵

¹Erciyes University, Halil Bayraktar Health Services Vocational College, Kayseri, Türkiye

²Erciyes University, Drug Application and Research Center, 38280, Kayseri, Türkiye

³Selcuk University, Department of Biology, Science Faculty, Konya, Türkiye

⁴Munzur University, Pertek Sakine Genç Vocational School, Pertek, Tunceli, Türkiye

⁵Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of NoviSad, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

* senguluysal@erciyes.edu.tr

Abstract

Euphorbia macroclada, belonging to the Euphorbiaceae family, has been used in folk medicine to treat various diseases (Ertas et al. 2015). This study aimed to evaluate the effect of solvents (ethyl acetate, methanol, and water) on bioactive compounds and antioxidant activities of *E. macroclada*. The total phenolic and flavonoid content of *E. macroclada* extracts was assessed using colorimetric methods. Phenolic compounds in the extracts were identified by HPLC analysis. Antioxidant capacity was determined by several *in vitro* methods including DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl), ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid), CUPRAC (Cupric reducing antioxidant capacity), and FRAP (ferric reducing antioxidant power). The methanol extract had the highest phenolic (78.93 mgGAE/g) and flavonoid (75.21 mgRE/g) content. The predominated phenolic compound in ethyl acetate and methanol extracts was catechin, whereas rutin was the predominant phenolic compound in water extract. Methanol extract displayed the strongest antioxidant capacity. These findings suggest *E. macroclada* is a promising natural source of antioxidants.

[1] A. Ertas, M.A. Yilmaz, M. Firat, Chemical profile by LC–MS/MS, GC/MS and antioxidant activities of the essential oils and crude extracts of two *Euphorbia* species. Natural Product Research, 2015, 29(6), 529-534.

Key words: *Euphorbia*, antioxidant, phenolic

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Erciyes University Scientific Research Projects Coordination Unit, Turkey (Project Number: THD-2025-14472).

VALORIZATION OF STRAWBERRY WASTE USING ULTRASOUND ASSISTED EXTRACTION AND ANN MODELLING

Milena Terzić^{1*}, Biljana Lončar¹, Aleksandra Cvetanović Kljakić¹, Gokhan Zengin², Jelena Arsenijević³, Slavica Ražić³

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²Selcuk University, Science Faculty, Konya, Turkey

³University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Vojvode Stepe 450, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

* milenavujanovic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Strawberry pomace, an important by-product of juice production, is a rich source of bioactive compounds with promising applications in the food, nutraceutical and pharmaceutical industries. This study focused on the optimization of ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) of phenol-rich extracts from strawberry waste and the evaluation of their antioxidant and enzyme inhibitory activities. The extractions were carried out under varying conditions of time, temperature and plant-solvent ratio. The results included total phenolic (TP) and flavonoid (TF) content, antioxidant capacity (DPPH, ABTS, CUPRAC, FRAP, MH, PM) and enzyme inhibition (AChE, BChE, tyrosinase, α -amylase, α -glucosidase). Strong correlations were observed between phenolic content and antioxidant potential, while enzyme inhibition appeared to be determined by different phytochemical groups. Principal component and cluster analyzes confirmed the separation between antioxidant and enzyme inhibitory responses. Artificial neural network (ANN) models were developed to predict and optimize the extraction results, with excellent prediction performance ($r^2 > 0.99$). Both ANN-based optimization and Z-score analysis identified 20 min UAE at 50 °C with a 1:20 plant:solvent ratio as the optimal extraction condition, producing extracts with high combined antioxidant and enzyme inhibitory activities. Overall, this study demonstrates that UAE in conjunction with ANN modeling is an effective strategy for process optimization and functional profiling of agricultural by-products and provides a sustainable route for the valorization of strawberry pomace into high-value bioactive ingredients.

Key words: *strawberry pomace, ultrasound-assisted extraction, artificial neural networks, biological potential*

Acknowledgment: *This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, GRANT No 7464, Novel Bio-linked Magnetite/geopolymer Composites in Phenol-containing Wastewater Treatment: Toward Zero-waste Technology – BioCompWaterClean.*

APPLE WASTE OPTIMIZATION USING ULTRASOUND ASSISTED EXTRACTION- MATHEMATICAL MODELLING APPROACH

Biljana Lončar^{1*}, Milena Terzić¹, Aleksadra Cvetanović Kljakić¹, Mirjana Petronijević¹, Gokhan Zengin², Jelena Arsenijević³, Slavica Ražić³

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²Selcuk University, Science Faculty, Konya, Turkey

³University of Belgrade, Faculty of Pharmacy, Vojvode Stepe 450, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

* cbiljana@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

The increasing generation of apple processing by-products presents a valuable opportunity for the recovery of bioactive compounds within a sustainable circular economy framework. This study aimed to optimize the ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) conditions for maximizing the recovery of phenolic compounds from apple pomace, using a mathematical modelling approach. The effects of extraction time (10–30 min), temperature (25–75 °C), and plant-to-solvent ratio (10–20 g/mL) were systematically evaluated across 15 experimental runs. Total phenolic content (TPC) and total flavonoid content (TFC) ranged from 4.70 to 9.97 mg GAE/g and 0.21 to 0.79 mg RE/g, respectively, indicating a significant influence of process variables ($p < 0.05$). The optimized conditions (10 min, 25 °C, 20 g/mL) yielded the highest TPC and TFC, aligning with superior antioxidant performance across DPPH, ABTS, CUPRAC, FRAP, metal chelating, and phosphomolybdenum assays. The extract exhibited strong radical scavenging capacity, particularly in samples 11A and 12A, with DPPH and ABTS values reaching 15.51 and 16.84 mg TE/g, respectively. Enzyme inhibition assays demonstrated moderate inhibition of AChE (2.58 mg GALAE/g) and tyrosinase (55.03 mg KAE/g), supporting potential applications in nutraceutical and cosmetic formulations. The developed mathematical model accurately described the influence of extraction parameters on bioactive yield and antioxidant response, confirming the efficiency of UAE as a green and scalable technology for apple waste valorization.

Key words: apple pomace, ultrasound-assisted extraction, mathematical modelling, standard score analysis, sustainable utilization.

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, GRANT No 7464, Novel Bio-linked Magnetite/geopolymer Composites in Phenol-containing Wastewater Treatment: Toward Zero-waste Technology – BioCompWaterClean.

ECO-FUNCTIONAL ACRYLAMIDE COPOLYMERS FOR SUSTAINABLE WASTEWATER TREATMENT

Jelena Tanasić^{1*}, Vladan Mičić², Ivan Ristić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of Technology, Zvornik, Bosnia and Herzegovina

* jelenatanasic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

The glowing contamination of aquatic systems with heavy metals and industrial effluents highlights the urgent need for innovative and sustainable water treatment technologies. Conventional purification methods, such as chemical precipitation or ion exchange, are often limited in selectivity, cost efficiency, and secondary waste generation. In this context, functionalized polymers enriched with active groups capable of chelation and adsorption represent one of the most promising approaches for advanced wastewater treatment.

In this study, copolymers based on acrylamide, acrylic acid and maleic acid were synthesized in aqueous solution using ammonium persulfate as the initiator. The aim was to increase the number of carboxyl (–COOH) groups (by maleic acid addition) to enhance the complexation capacity toward divalent cations. The synthesized copolymers were characterized using FTIR spectroscopy, viscometry, and gel permeation chromatography (GPC). FTIR spectra confirmed the presence of characteristic amide and carboxyl bands, while viscometry and GPC data indicated molecular weight values (M_n) between 3,850 and 71,250 g/mol, depending on synthesis conditions. A significant improvement in the CCDK (Capacity of Complexation with Divalent Cations) was observed with the introduction of maleic acid, reaching values up to 300 mg/g. This result confirms that the increased density of carboxyl groups notably improves metal ion binding efficiency.

Overall, the obtained copolymers exhibit desirable properties for use in water purification, combining high stability, tunable molecular characteristics, and strong affinity for metal ions. These findings suggest that acrylamide–maleic acid copolymers can serve as effective, environmentally friendly materials for wastewater treatment processes aimed at achieving zero-waste technology.

Key words: *acrylamide copolymers, maleic acid, FTIR, GPC, CCDK, wastewater treatment*

Acknowledgment: This work was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Republic of Serbia (project number 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200134 and 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200134) and Ministry of Scientific and Technological Development and Higher Education of the Republic of Srpska, through the project “Innovative Synthesis of New Polymeric Materials for Advanced Water Purification – Development and Application of Environmentally Sustainable Solutions,” contract number 19.030/3-2-5-1/24.

IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION OF A PHASED TRAINING COURSE FOR COMPREHENSIVE MICROPLASTIC ANALYSIS IN ENVIRONMENTAL SAMPLES

Vesna Teofilović^{1*}, Danka Radić², Snežana Štrbac³, Sebastian Primpke⁴, Nataša Stojić⁵

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Institute for General and Physical Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia

³University of Belgrade, Institute for Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade, Serbia

⁴Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, Germany

⁵University EDUCONS, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

* vesnateofilovic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Microplastic (MP) pollution requires the adoption of standardized, reliable analytical methods to accurately monitor environmental contamination and evaluate the performance of removal technologies. A significant challenge remains the lack of personnel trained in the complete analytical workflow. This abstract presents a structured, two-part training course designed to build capacity among researchers and laboratory staff, covering all essential steps for MP analysis in water and sediment. The core objective was to provide intensive, hands-on experience, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. The training was successfully delivered in two sequential phases: Part I (2023) focused on the necessary groundwork, covering protocols for the preparation and isolation of microplastic content in water and sediment. This included effective organic matter digestion, density separation techniques, and critical QA/QC measures. Part II (2024) built on these skills, providing practical instruction on the definitive identification of obtained microplastic particles using Raman and FTIR spectroscopy and specialized software for data processing. This phase covered instrument operation, spectrum interpretation, and polymer categorization. This successfully implemented phased course serves as an effective model for rapid capacity building. Upon completion, participants were equipped with the full set of competencies required to establish and conduct independent MP monitoring programs. The training directly contributes to the standardization of analytical protocols, enabling the generation of more reliable and intercomparable data vital for environmental management and regulatory decisions.

Key words: microplastics, density separation, organic matter digestion, FTIR, raman,

Acknowledgment: GREENLand — Twinning Microplastic-free Environment grant no. 101079267, Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation, Republic of Serbia, grants no. 451-03-136/2025-03/200134, 451-03-136/2025-03/200026, 451-03-136/2025-03/200051

ABOUT

BIOCOMPWATERCLEAN PROJECT

The overall goal of the BioCompWaterClean project is to raise the scientific and innovative excellence in the field of phenolic contaminants removal from wastewater contributing to national and regional scientific and economic growth and well-being. The main objective of the Project implies the utilization of novel bio-functionalized magnetite-geopolymer composites for the removal of phenolic compounds from wastewater. BioCompWaterClean implements smart biowaste management principles in order to synthesize functionalized composites performing as valuable adsorbents/biocatalysts for wastewater treatment. In line with the principles of green and sustainable chemistry, the synthetic routes are being optimized toward minimization of energy and raw materials consumption. An additional element of the implemented smart biowaste management will include the proposed solution for the disposal of solid waste material remained after water treatment processes by its incorporation into the construction material. Therefore, the development of novel adsorbents/biocatalysts for phenolic wastewater treatment by combining the fundamental knowledge with tools of smart biowaste management will provide new opportunities for the development of modern lines for the purification of municipal and industrial wastewater, as well as the improvement of already existing water treatment systems, all in an attempt to reach zero-waste technology. The knowledge gained within this project will strengthen the scientific capacities of individual institutions and their participants, and by its extensive dissemination the collaboration with interested stakeholders will be intensified. This will create excellent starting conditions toward the establishment of circular economy in the wastewater treatment sector.

Full project title: Novel Bio-linked Magnetite/geopolymer Composites in Phenol-containing Wastewater Treatment: Toward Zero-waste Technology

Funded by: The Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia, Program PRISMA, #grant № 7464

PI: Prof. Slavica Ražić, PhD

Project leader: University of Belgrade – Faculty of Pharmacy

Partner institutions: University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Sciences, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Civil Engineering, University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Technical Sciences

Website: <https://biocompwaterclean.org/>